

Journal of Advanced Research and Transformative Knowledge
ISSN: 2468-1357 Website: www.jartk.com Vol 12, Issue 12, 2021

**COST BEHAVIOR ANALYSIS AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE
OF MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES IN RWANDA: A CASE STUDY
OF BRALIRWA PLC.**

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
ACADEMIC REQUIREMENTS OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE
AWARD OF MASTER'S DEGREE IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION**

KIGALI INDEPENDENT UNIVERSITY ULK.

DECEMBER, 2021

DECLARATION

I, MUKABATSINDA M. Claire hereby declare that this research work entitled the “*Cost Behavior Analysis and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Industries in Rwanda: a case study of Bralirwa Plc*” is my original work, and has not been submitted for any award anywhere else by the student or any other person. All the sources used or quoted have been indicated and acknowledged by complete references.

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APPROVAL

This is to certify that this research work entitled the “*Cost Behavior Analysis and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Industries in Rwanda: a case study of Bralirwa Plc*” is a work done by MUKABATSINDA M. Claire under my guidance and supervision.

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. MBONIGABA Celestin

Date...../...../.....

Signature.....

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to: my lovely husband, and children, parents, sisters and brothers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, special thanks go to Almighty God for His grace, keeping me healthy, enormous love, guidance, protection and blessings during my life at large and studies. I warmly thank the Founder of ULK, the top management, and all academic staff for their help in academic matters. I will always remain grateful for their offered academic values. Sincere appreciation and great honor are expressed to my supervisor, Prof. Dr. MBONIGABA Celestin for his valuable professional guidance, intellectual coaching, scientific constructive criticism, monitoring, sacrifice and careful supervision. I appreciate ULK staff especially different lectures in my departments who taught me until when I have accomplished my academic courses. I would like to appreciate all those who are contributing moral and financial support to this research project.

MUKABATSINDA M. CLAIRE

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS, AND ACRONYMS

CCC	Cash Conversion Cycle
CEO	Chef Executive Officer
COGS	Cost of Goods Sold
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease-2019
CVI	Content Validity Index
EAC	East Africa Community
GPM	Gross Profit Margin
IAS	International Accounting Standards
IFRS	International Financial Reporting Standards
NI	Net Income
NS	Net Sales
R&D	Research and Development
RDB	Rwanda Development Boards
ROA	Return On Assets
ROE	Return On Equity
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
ULK	Kigali Independent University
USA	United States of America

ABSTRACT

*The study was about cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda: case study of Bralirwa Plc in the period of 2017-2020. The issue is that Rwanda industries are not achieving properly their objectives and goals, where many reasons are considered to threatening industries' objectives: some of them are winding up due to ignoring cost behavior analysis practices in financial performance process, lack of better knowledge about management accounting and many industries are in trouble. The specific objectives of this study were examining the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; to analyze the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; evaluating the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; and identifying the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda. This study applied the cross-sectional survey design of quantitative approach. Target population is 201 employees in management team in charge of cost behavior analysis and financial performance of Bralirwa Plc, Kigali Rwanda. The stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to select 67 respondents from Bralirwa Plc. Primary data were collected using questionnaires while secondary data was conducted by accessing the published documents including financial reports of Bralirwa Plc. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistical were used in this study. Key findings displayed that there is a positive and very strong correlation between material cost analysis in cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries as a Pearson correlation is .895** with the p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. There is positive and very strong correlation between labor cost analysis and the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc as Pearson correlation is .885** with p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. The results revealed that there is positive and strong correlation between overheads cost analysis and financial performance of Bralirwa Plc, Rwanda as Pearson correlation is .556** with p-value is 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. Based to the findings, the problem of this study was solved, the research objectives were achieved, and research hypotheses were verified where all null hypotheses were rejected, while alternative hypothesis were retained by saying that there is significance and very high relationship between cost behavior analysis represented by Material Cost analysis, Labor Cost analysis, Overheads Cost analysis; and financial performance of manufacturing industries (Bralirwa Plc) in Rwanda. Bralirwa Plc should use comparative analysis using comparison with other companies in the industry. Bralirwa Plc has to improve the skills of the employees working in the cost analysis.*

Key words: *Cost Behavior Analysis, Material Cost analysis, Labor Cost analysis, Overheads Cost analysis, financial Performance*

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION OF THE STUDY

Knowledge of cost behavior is very important, especially for decision-making. The cost behavior is associated with learning how costs change when there is a change in an organization's level of activity. It is important to understand the cost behavior in company so the company's management which is able to make the right decision in the sphere of planning and managing the costs that could be a leading channel of financial performance in future.

Despite the important of cost behavior analysis to the companies, most of them are lacking of management accounting practices for decision making followed by lacking technical skills for cost behavior analysis are as much obstacles to developing manufacturing companies as is the inability to access credit. There is an increase also problems of ineffective management costs practices, products delayed, distorted, or too highly aggregated information that can easily undermine the efforts of companies with excellent research and development, production, and marketing activities.

This chapter illustrated the background of study; problem statement; research objectives; research questions; research hypotheses, scope of the study; significance of study; definitions of key terms and structure of the thesis.

1.1. Background of the Study

In worldwide, cost management is one of the most significant issues for many companies at any stage of its development. Nowadays, companies try to reduce their costs across the whole firm, from administration to production (Maher *et al.*, 2008). However, cost management does not mean only cost reduction, but it is also a process that should lead to better use of costs and higher production volumes and revenues (Shim, & Siegel, 2009). In developed countries like USA and

Europe, costing methods, techniques and systems represent the key instruments for measuring business performance for their companies (Pichetkun, & Panmanee, 2012).

The cost classification in cost analysis in developed countries stated above, i.e. costs are placed into defined categories according to their given characteristics. It is important to note that traditional and standard appraisal of cost behavior, measured purely by the volume of production or sales, would not seem up to the job of meeting the current needs of manufacturing enterprises. Managers are interested in estimating previous cost behavior patterns, since this information can accelerate more precise cost forecasts concerning the planning and decision-making (Pichetkun, & Panmanee, 2012).

In Sub-Sahara of Africa companies, Cost management is a process of quality planning and cost decreasing that manages the costs before its occurrence (Ansari *et al*, 2010). The limited resource and apparent continuous competition influence firms to better managing cost of production by implementing standard costing, budget system, monitoring cost information, and focusing on value added activities by eliminating non-value added activities through supplier coordination, and emphasizing on cost structure by analyzing cost and finding the way to reduce costs in the stage of pre-production. Traditional cost management and cost plus pricing strategies have also lost their influence in this new competitive environment. Because most of the costs are determined in projection and development phase, traditional cost management approaches which consider only the costs in production phase and disregard the other costs in production life cycle have lost the importance (Ansari *et al*, 2010).

According to Aysan (2006), Turkish accounting profession has been in progress since the establishment of Turkish Republic. As a result of industrialization, the need for accounting

profession emerged. For this reason, the business managers and management accountants needed in private companies were mostly transferred from State Economic Enterprises. Manufacturing companies have an important role to play in Ghana's socioeconomic development. The extent of contribution these business units can make towards the growth and development of Ghana is dependent on the level of success attained by their operations. Fact is that, underlying the success of a business enterprise are the establishment and application of controls by the owners or management in addition to the systematic record keeping of business transactions, which, at the end of the period, keeps the owner well-informed about the performance of the business (John & Ben, 2011).

It is important to note that, in Nigerian manufacturing companies are facing a lot of challenges, which affect profitability. These challenges have constituted threats to the growth and survival of this level of businesses. It is apparent that many of SMEs have gone into oblivion due to intolerable and unacceptable decadent forms of infrastructural developments. The poor state of the country's basic infrastructure has not been resolved and so it becomes difficult for small and medium scale enterprise to thrive. Basic enabling environment includes good roads, stable electricity; pipe borne water, communication facilities and security system (Oghojafor, 2013)

In Uganda, Britania Allied Industries Ltd is located at plot M247B Ntinda Industrial Area, Kampala Uganda. This place is approximately 9km from the city center Kampala. The Britania biscuit manufacturing in Kampala, was set up in 1991 by the House of Dawda group a group which has been in existence since 1962 in the East African region pioneered by Hasmukh Dawda Britania Allied Industries Ltd was created through the merger of operating subsidiaries Britania are in business of manufacturing biscuits; confectionery; fruit juices and sauces Britania have highly

reliable process equipment and methods in all production facilities. Tetra Pak for fruit juices and auto filling machines are a few to mention. Late 2002, the company acquired the present Manji Food Industries Ltd, biscuit factory at Nairobi. Britannia owes its success to its creative, determined, dependable and enterprising people and the cooperation of an extensive network of customers and partners. Data monitor magazine (2005), due to liberalization, the manufacturing sector is characterized by several players, increased competition, regulatory changes, changing consumers styles and expectations, availability of a wide variety of substitutes, shorter distribution techniques as manufacturers gain direct access to most markets increased costs of advertising and distribution outlets demand higher rebates. The industry faces increased competition from imported substitutes both in price and quality (Bello, *et al.*, 2002).

According to Waddock and Graves (2011), financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The study seeks to establish how financial performance of manufacturing and allied firms are affected by the level of working capital investment, capital structure choices and the investment decisions undertaken by the firms. This term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period of time, and can be used to compare similar firms across the same industry or to compare industries or sectors in aggregation. The subject of financial performance has always been of great interest to scholars and still remains an area of great concern to the business practitioners of all types of organizations.

According to Huselid (2010) financial performance has been measured in various ways, items in income and cash flow statement as well statement of financial position can be used for example liquidity measures the ability of the business to meet its financial obligations as they fall due without affecting the company's normal business operations, it also provide an indication of the

business ability to withstand risks by providing information about the operation's ability to continue operating after a major financial adversity. Profitability analysis focuses on the relationship between revenues and expenses and on the level of profits relative to the size of investment in the business for instance return on sales shows how much a firm earns in relation to its sales, return on assets (ROA) shows firm's ability to make use of its assets and return on equity (ROE) reveals the return on investments (Roberts & Dowling, 2012).

According to Ntui *et al.*, (2014), since Tanzania differs from developed and other developing countries in terms of capital markets, economy and infrastructural development, this limited evidence in the context of Tanzania. In Tanzania, business plays a vital role in the capital formation of a country and people consider it as the life blood of a growing economy. Therefore, it is very important to manage business effectively and efficiently. One of the major issues encountered by fund managers today in Tanzania is not the procurement of funds but also their meaningful deployment to generate maximum returns (Mohammad, 2013). Cost control is an important corporate financial decision since it directly affects the profitability of the firm. Working capital management efficiency is vital especially for manufacturing firms, where a major part of assets is composed of current assets especially inventory and trade receivables (Arunkumar & Ramanan, 2013).

In Rwanda's case, accounting profession has grown tremendously with the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and International Accounting Standards (IAS) as accounting and auditing standards. Over the years, the challenge to keep costs down in order to keep better performance has been predominant in most companies and especially those listed on the Rwanda Development Boards (RDB) given the pressure from the shareholders for firms to post better performance. With the overall economic situation in Rwanda, investors are looking for

companies that can create wealth for them hence companies which perform poorly do not attract investors. Management accounting offers the best opportunity for firms to compete in the market in order to offer best quality products and services at affordable prices to consumers. Most of the existing research literature on accounting in Rwanda manufacturing companies tends to be more biased toward the arm of financial accounting, information technology adoption as well as research in credit accessibility for manufacturing companies, more so only remote exists in regard to effects of management accounting practices on financial performance of manufacturing companies in Rwanda (Alleyne, 2010).

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite the available strategies to managing costs, companies still show stagnant or deteriorating performance on nonfinancial indicators are unlikely to become or long remain world-class competitors in the name of failure to implement such strategies. Present cost management control systems rest on concepts developed almost a century ago when the nature of competition and the demands for internal information were very different from what they are today. After all developments and changes, in order to survive and make profit in global competitive environment. Manufacturing companies have started to question their traditional and cost management systems with the aim of adaptation to global competition and supplying quick changing demands and expectations of consumers. Traditional cost management and cost plus pricing strategies have also lost their influence in this new competitive environment. Because most of the costs are determined in projection and development phase, traditional cost management approaches which consider only the costs in production phase and disregard the other costs in production life cycle have lost the importance (Adler, 2012).

Cost management is a process of quality planning and cost decreasing that manages the costs before its occurrence (Ansari et al., 2009). Limited resource and apparent continuous competition influence firms to better managing cost of production by implementing standard costing, budget system, monitoring cost information, and focusing on value added activities by eliminating non-value added activities through supplier coordination, and emphasizing on cost structure by analyzing cost and finding the way to reduce costs in the stage of pre-production. Firms with cost management strategy implementation are able to know when the amount of cost will incur in the future if they have current and future cost information. So far no local research which determines the direct impact of cost management strategies on financial performance of manufacturing companies has been done (Ansari *et al.*, 2009).

Rwanda industries are not achieving properly their objectives and goals, where many reasons are considered to threatening industries' objectives: some of them are winding up due to ignoring cost behavior analysis practices in financial performance process, lack of better knowledge about management accounting and many industries are in trouble. Some of manufacturing industries' product grow slowly and others grow negatively and managers have a big challenge of developing management costs practices on financial performance (Jonhson, 2015). It is therefore this study is undertaken to evaluate on how does cost behavior analysis affect financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda, BRALIRWA Plc.

1.3. Research Objectives

This study has two categories of objectives: general objective and specific objectives.

1.3.1 General Objective

The study assessed the cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of this study were in four ways as follows.

- i. To analyze the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda
- ii. To examine the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda
- iii. To find out the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda
- iv. To identify the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

1.4. Research Questions

To achieve the above objectives, this study answered the following questions.

1. What are the effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda?
2. What are the effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda?
3. What are the effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda?
4. What is the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda?

1.5. Research Hypotheses

In this study, research hypotheses verified null and alternative hypotheses.

1. **Ho1:** There are no significant effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

H1: There are positive and significant effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

2. **Ho2:** There are no significant effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

H2: There are positive and significant effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

3. **Ho3:** There are no significant effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

H3: There are positive and significant effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

4. **Ho4:** There is no significant relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

H4: There is positive and significant relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

1.6. Scope of the study

This study has been limited in the following angles.

1.6.1 Content

The study is in domain of managerial accounting; it assessed the cost behavior analysis and performance of manufacturing companies in Rwanda.

1.6.2 Geographical

This study was conducted in BRALIRWA Plc located at Gatenga, Kicukiro District, and Kigali city. It was chosen because BRALIRWA Plc, Part of the Heineken Company, is engaged in the production, distribution and sales of a wide range of beer and beverage brands.

Bralirwa Plc is a public company limited by shares since 9th June 2010 incorporated in the Republic of Rwanda under the law no7/2009 of 27th April 2009 relating to companies and registered by the Registrar General Office under no 100004348. It was the first company listed on the Rwanda Stock Exchange (RSE) as from 31st January, 2011.

1.6.3 Time

The study evaluates the situation of 4years, this means from 2017 to 2020 where the researcher looked the annual financial analysis reports of these stated periods from BRALIRWA Plc.

1.7. Significance of the Study

This study is very useful to individual, social, scientists and academicians. To the researcher, this study is useful for researcher not only to obtain master's degree, but also to improve her knowledge on the subject under study (cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing companies) where the researcher is able to put theories applied in classroom to the practical work in this study.

To the BRALIRWA Plc; this study would help decision makers and cost managers of BRALIRWA Plc find real position through knowing their weaknesses in costs analysis and the way to correct them referring to the recommendations and suggestions would be provided in this study.

Scientifically, findings of this study would be a future reference document to the next generation of different Universities especially ULK while academically, this study adds valuable knowledge

to existing studies related to the cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing companies by completing the scarcity of studies in area of Rwanda.

1.8. Definitions of Key Concepts

Cost behavior analysis

According to (Anderson, M., & Janakiraman, S., 2004) cost behavior analysis refers to management's attempt to understand how operating costs change in relation to a change in an organization's level of activity. These costs may include direct materials, direct labor, and overhead costs that are incurred from developing a product.

Management typically performs cost behavior analysis through mathematical cost functions. Cost functions are descriptions of how a cost (e.g., material, labor, or overhead) changes with changes in the level of activity relating to that cost.

Fixed costs remain constant over a certain time interval and are unaffected by changes in the volume of output. Variable costs change more or less in direct proportion with changes in the level of output. Semi-variable costs include partly fixed and partly variable elements. For decision-making purposes, it is normally necessary to split such costs into their fixed and variable elements (Hansen, 2009).

Financial performance

According to Will Kenton (2021) financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period.

Key performance indicators tied to the financials typically focus on revenue and profit margins.

Net profit, the most tried and true of profit-based measurements, represents the amount of revenue

that remains, as profit for a given period, after accounting for all of the company's expenses, taxes, and interest payments for the same period.

Manufacturing companies

According to Granta Park, (2020) Manufacturing is the production of goods through the use of labor, machinery, tools and biological or chemical processing or formulation.

Manufacturing can either mean transforming raw materials into finished goods on a large scale, or the creation of more complex items by selling basic goods to manufacturers for the production of items such as automobiles, aircraft, or household appliances.

Raw materials are transformed into finished products through manufacturing engineering or the manufacturing process. This process begins with product design and materials selection. The materials are modified during various manufacturing processes to create the finished product. Modern advanced manufacturing often includes several intermediate processes to create the various components for a finished item, with some manufacturers using the term fabrication. Manufacturing has close connections to the engineering and industrial process design sectors.

1.9 Structure of the Thesis

Considering content scope, this thesis was divided into five chapters outlined as chapter one is introduction to the study that consists of background to the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, research questions, research hypothesis, scope of the study, significance of the study, definition of key concepts and its structure.

Chapter two examines pertinent literature review introducing concepts, theories and models and reviews past studies from the global point down to the economic context. Chapter three explains research design and methodology comprises target number to analyse, statistical design, data

collection and analysis. Chapter four presented research findings and their discussions. Chapter five brought the research to the summary, conclusion, and recommendations.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter provides an understanding on related literature for assesses cost behavior analysis and performance of manufacturing companies from the written of other previous researchers and authors.

It showed an overview on the conceptual framework, theoretical perspectives, and the related empirical studies. The study identified the gaps left by previous authors, and thereafter, proposes the way on how to fill those gaps.

2.1 Conceptual and Ttheoretical Perspectives

2.1.1 Cost Behavior Analysis

According to (Roberts & Dowling, 2012) an understanding of how organization's costs vary with changes in the level of output may be extremely useful when confronted with a range of managerial decisions.

For example, an understanding of cost behavior helped management to prepare its budgets, decide whether to make or buy a component, determine what level of output and sales are necessary to break even or to make a certain level of profit, and determine whether a given division or plant is making a positive contribution to the firm's profitability.

The cost behaviour included by fixed costs; variable costs; semi-variable costs; independent variables; and dependent variables. Before one can begin to understand how a business is going to perform over time and with shifts in volume, it is imperative to first consider the cost structure of the business. This requires drilling down into the specific types of costs that are to be incurred and trying to understand their unique attributes (Yasukata, K., 2011).

2.1.1.1 Variable Costs

Variable costs vary in direct proportion to changes in the level of an activity. For example, direct material, direct labor, sales commissions, fuel cost for a trucking company, and so on, may be expected to increase with each additional unit of output (Horngren, C. *et al.*, 2006).

The activity base is the item or event that causes the incurrence of a variable cost. It is easy to think of the activity base in terms of units produced, but it can be more than that. Activity can relate to labor hours worked, units sold, customers processed, or other such “cost drivers”. Each variable cost must be considered independently and with careful attention to what activity drives the cost (Iacob, C., *et al.*, 2007).

2.1.1.2 Fixed Costs

The opposite of variable costs are fixed costs. Fixed costs do not fluctuate with changes in the level of activity. The rent is said to be a “fixed” cost, because total rent not change as output rises and falls. The following spreadsheet reveals the factory rent incurred at different levels of production and the resulting “per unit” rent amount. The fixed cost per unit decline with increases in production. This attribute of fixed costs is important to consider in assessing the scalability of a business proposition. There are numerous types of fixed costs. Examples include administrative salaries, rents, property taxes, security, networking infrastructure support, and so forth (Călin, O. *et al.*, 2008).

2.1.1.3 Mixed Costs

According to (Kester, 2010) many costs contain both variable and fixed components. These costs are called mixed or semi variable. If you have a cell phone, you probably know more than you wish about such items. Cell phone agreements usually provide for a monthly fee plus usage charges

for excess minutes, text messages, and so forth. With a mixed cost, there is some fixed amount plus a variable component tied to an activity. Mixed costs are harder to evaluate, because they change in response to fluctuations in volume.

The costs associated with manufacturing can be classified into three broad groups: materials, labour and overheads. Essentially, materials are the physical items that are used to manufacture a product. Those that are directly in evidence in the finished product are referred to as direct materials. The other materials are referred to as indirect, because they cannot be attributed to a single product, or it is too costly to try and determine the amount attributed to each product (Michael, 2012).

As with materials, it is possible to classify labour as either direct or indirect. Direct labour refers to labour which is employed in the manufacture of the firm's products. Indirect labour refers to that part of the firms' labor costs that cannot be directly attributed to the production process and might include maintenance staff, cleaners, storekeepers, etc. A firm may decide that some labour costs are indirect because the cost or effort required to determine the direct amount attributable to specific products is too great.

Overhead costs are somewhat difficult to define precisely. Basically, they include all costs associated with the manufacture of products that have not been included as either direct materials or direct labor. In this sense, overhead costs are a residual item. They might include such expenses as the depreciation of machinery, insurance of buildings and machinery, heating, electricity, etc. It is also important to distinguish between factory overheads and other overheads (Livingstone, 2011).

Supplies to the factory manager's office would be manufacturing overheads, whereas supplies for the sales manager's office would be classified as a selling expense. An important characteristic of overhead costs is the difficulty in attributing them directly to specific units of product. The essential difference between variable and absorption costing relates to the way in which they treat these overhead costs, particularly those costs which are regarded as fixed, at least in the short run.

Variable costing is an inventory valuation method that assigns only direct materials, direct labour and variable manufacturing overhead costs to the units of production produced in a given period. All other manufacturing costs, such as fixed manufacturing overheads, variable and fixed selling and administration costs are treated as period costs (Gibendi, 2013).

Absorption costing is an inventory valuation system that assigns all manufacturing costs such as direct materials, direct labour, variable manufacturing overheads and fixed manufacturing overheads to the units of output produced in a given period. The allocation of fixed overhead costs to products is undertaken in the belief that all costs associated with providing manufacturing facilities in a given period should be incorporated in the cost of units manufactured during the period (Eleonora, & Maurizio B., 2012).

The essential difference between these two alternative methods is that under variable costing, the fixed costs are treated as a period cost and are not incorporated in the cost of individual products, whereas under absorption costing fixed costs are clearly regarded as product costs and are included in the determination of each unit's manufacturing costs. From a financial accounting perspective, it is argued that absorption costing is consistent with generally accepted accounting principles. These alternative approaches to income measurement and inventory valuation give rise to slightly different income statements.

Under variable costing, the determination of manufacturing costs and the income statement has the following form: 1. direct materials; 2. direct labor; and 3. variable overheads: work in process inventory; finished goods inventory; and costs of goods sold inventory. Sales include cost of goods sold (only variable manufacturing costs); fixed manufacturing overhead; non-production costs (variable and fixed); and net income (Oberholzer & Ziemerink, 2004).

2.1.2 Financial performance of manufacturing companies

According to Penman (2009) financial performance as the level of performance of a business over a specified period of time, expressed in terms of overall profits and losses during that time. Evaluating the financial performance of a business allows decision-makers to judge the results of business strategies and activities in objective monetary terms. A subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues.

According to Penman (2009) there are many different ways to measure financial performance, but all measures should be taken in aggregation. Some of the indicators of financial performance are return on equity, liquidity ratios, asset management ratios, profitability ratios, leverage ratios and market value ratios.

Petersen and Kumar (2010) noted that the other financial indicators of financial performance include: sales growth, return on investment, return on sales and earnings per share. The popular ratios that measure organizational performance is summarized as profitability and growth: return on asset, return on investment, return on equity, return on sale, revenue growth, market shares, stock price, sales growth, liquidity and operational efficiency (Petersen & Kumar, 2010).

Performance is dignified by exhausting the profitability ratio, where the amount of money have been gained or increased when they are salaried more for something than it cost you to make, get,

or do it. It is an excess of revenues over expenditures and expenses in a business enterprise over a given period of time, usually a year or the monetary gain derived from a transaction. Revenues are measured as the amount of money that a business actually obtains during a specific period, including discounts and deductions for repaid merchandise, and it remains the top line or gross income amount from which costs are deducted to regulate net income (Drury, 2004).

The expenses are pragmatic of money spent or cost experienced in an administration's efforts to make revenue, demonstrating the cost of doing business. There stay different dimension factors of profit evolution used by investigative a business' performance like gross profit margin (GPM), return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) (Elliot, *et al.*, 2005).

2.1.2.1. Net profit margin (NPM)

It computes the proportion of each sale dollar that remains after deducting interest, dividend, taxes, expenses and costs. In other words, it computes the fraction of profit a business that remains earning in contradiction of its sale. Higher value of return on sale displays the improved performance. $NPM = (\text{Earnings} / \text{Net sales}) * 100$ (Elliot, *et al.*, 2005).

Profit margin is envisioned with selling price (or revenue) occupied as base times 100. It is the percentage of selling price that is revolved into profit, whereas profit measurement or markup remains the percentage of cost price that one gets as profit on top of cost price. While marketing somewhat one knows what proportion of profit becomes on a specific investment. So businesses compute profit percentage to find the ratio of profit to cost (Gloy, & LaDue, 2003).

2.1.2.2. Gross Profit Margin

Gross margin discusses ahe profit of goods and services. It expresses how much it charges to yield the product. It is planned by dividing gross profit margin (GPM) by net sales (NS) and multiplying

the proportion by 100: $\text{Gross Profit Margin} = \text{Gross Profit}/\text{Net Sales} \times 100$ or $\text{GM} = \text{GP}/\text{NS} \times 100$ (Birrell, 2014).

2.1.2.3. Return on Assets

Return on Asset is designed by dividing net income (NI) for the current year by the value of all the corporation's assets (A) and multiplying the quotient by 100. The return on assets (ROA) displays the percentage of how profitable a business's assets remain in producing revenue (Bryman, 2008). $\text{Return on Assets} = \text{Net Income}/\text{Assets} \times 100$ or $\text{ROA} = \text{NI}/\text{TA} \times 100$. Or $\text{ROA} = \text{Net Income} / \text{Average of Total Asset}$

2.1.2.4. Return on Equity

Return on equity measures how much a business makes for each dollar that investors put into it. You calculate it by taking the net income earned (NI) by the amount of money invested by shareholders (SI) and multiplying the quotient by 100: $\text{Return on equity} = \text{Net income}/\text{shareholder investment} \times 100$ or $\text{ROE} = \text{NI}/\text{SI} \times 100$ (Charles, 2003).

ROE is especially used for comparing the performance of businesses in the same manufacturing. As with return on capital, a ROE stays a measure of organization's ability to make income from the equity accessible to it (Rotblut, 2013).

2.1.2.5. Current Ratio

Current ratio is calculated by dividing the total current assets by total current liability. $\text{Current ratio} = \text{current asset}/\text{current liability}$. Acid test ratio or quick ratio is the true liquidity mentions the ability of a firm to recompense its short-term obligations when they become due. It is the ratio of liquid assets to current liabilities (Fabozzi, 2009).

The current ratio is probably the best known and most often used of the liquidity ratios, which experts and stockholders use to assess the business's ability to pay its short-term debt

responsibilities, such as accounts payable (payments to suppliers) and taxes and wages. Short-term records payable to a bank, for illustration, may be pertinent. The current ratio displays how many times over the firm can pay its current debt obligations based on its current, most liquid assets. The current ratio is designed from balance sheet data using the following formula: Current ratio = Current assets / current liabilities (Rosemary, 2019).

2.1.2.6. Quick ratio

The quick ratio stays a more severe test of liquidity than the current ratio formula. Inventory is the least liquid of all the current assets because you have to find a buyer for your inventory. Finding a buyer, especially in a slow economy, is not always possible.

Therefore, companies need to be able to come across their short-term debt obligations by using cash and counterparts, without having to rely on selling inventory. The formula is as follows Quick Ratio = current assets-inventory / current liabilities (Rosemary, 2019).

Quick Ratio or acid test is totaled the current asset-inventory/current liabilities. It is very useful in calculating the liquidity position of a firm. It measures the company's capacity to pay off current obligations immediately and is more rigorous test of liquidity than the current ratio (Brock, & Rojas, 2000).

2.1.3 Management accounting theory of cost behavior

Management accounting contains a number of decisions-making tools that require the conversion of all operating costs and expenses into fixed and variable components. The responsibility for providing this cost behavior information falls squarely upon the shoulders of the management accountant. The conversion of ordinary financial data as typically found in the general ledger accounts requires that the management accountant have a thorough understanding of cost behavior theory (Weiss, D., 2010).

The identification and measurement of fixed and variable costs is somewhat complicated by the fact that some costs are fixed or variable at the discretion of management, while other costs are not. Furthermore, for those expenditures that are inherently variable, management has the ability, within limits, to control the magnitude of the variable cost factors. In order to exercise this control, management also needs a solid understanding of the nature of cost behavior. The usefulness of fixed and variable cost data depends on the validity of these assumptions. In order to avoid poor operating results and faulty decision making that is likely to occur when false cost assumptions are made, the ability to recognize and measure cost behavior is essential (Dalla Via, & Perego, 2014).

2.2 Review of related studies

According to Oberholzer and Ziemerink, (2004), Cost behavior classification and cost behavior structures of manufacturing companies. The purpose of this paper is to determine the cost structures of companies that formed part of an empirical investigation. Further aspects were investigated to determine why manufacturing companies classify cost behavior into fixed and variable components and to determine how these companies classify specific cost items. It was found that there is a significant negative relationship between the fixed cost of a company and its degree of technological development. This means that labor-intensive companies have more fixed cost as part of total costs and therefore a higher operating risk than technologically developed companies. It was also found that manufacturing companies classify cost items differently and this study provides some guidelines how to manage cost behavior.

Eduardo Hebling *et al.*, (2013) assessed the total cost of direct and indirect materials used in Class III, IV and V composite resin direct restorations. Methods, the calculation of costs was based on the method of variable costing system. A list of the materials was obtained by a panel of experts

and based on the excellence standards established in the literature for dental team treatment. The cost considered for each material was obtained from an average of the costs found in the regional supplier market (US\$1.0=R\$2.12). The repetitions were obtained from Class III, IV and V cavities in artificial pre-manufactured teeth. The cavities were classified as shallow, medium and deep. The materials were quantified for each type of preparation. Seven brands of composite resins were used and weighed on a precision scale after their insertion in each cavity. The data were analyzed by descriptive statistics and non-parametric Friedman's test ($\alpha=0.05$). Results, the mean costs were US\$7.96 (R\$16.88) for Class III restoration, US\$8.13 (R\$17.24) for Class IV, and US\$7.84 (R\$16.62) for Class V. There was statistically significant difference in cost between the types of cavities and depth classification. The small cost difference among the different resin brands resulted in no statistically significant differences in the total cost of the restorations. Conclusions: The costs obtained in this survey may be used in the calculation of the final cost of restorative procedures, helping in the management of public or private dental care services.

According to Novák, and Strouhal (2017) cost management is one of the most significant issues in company performance and company financial management which any enterprise has to solve as in the periods of declines of sales revenues, as well as during their growth. In this study they designed and tested several regression models that could be suitable for cost behavior prediction and subsequent decision-making based on these predictions. They used multiple linear regression models with a point estimate and with interval estimate of the model parameters. Comparison of regression models of cost behavior and their reliability was carried out due to the quality of the data collected for the case of basic and adjusted data. The overheads were divided into several groups of relevant costs and their dependences were examined on different factors other than only the production volume using the correlation matrix. From the results of the transformed model

they believe that asymmetric cost behavior is affected by asymmetric behavior of the chosen factors. As the final one was intended the model representing the change in costs in time shifting about one-month period. This model can be used for examining costs in time shift by a short period (e.g., months) and thus it is possible to prove cost asymmetric behavior called "sticky costs". They used the model adjusted in accordance with Anderson et al., (2003) and we kept the model clearly transformed and assembled so that there remained only those variables that had a statistically significant effect on the dependent variable.

According to Florence M. and Patrick M. (2018) effect of corporate diversification on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Rwanda: a case study of selected manufacturing firms. The operating environment for business has become very volatile and dynamic innovation and globalization. This has meant that organizations have to constantly be ready to develop and implement new strategies that would boost their competitiveness. Diversification is developing as one of the most important growth have adopted diversification strategies have succeeded while others have failed. The study sought to determine the effect of corporate diversification on the financial performance of manufacturing in Rwanda. To achieve this objective the study used a descriptive survey. A census approach was used, and secondary data was used for five years (2012) statements and records. Data analysis was done corporate diversification was positively related to financial performance of 15 selected manufacturing firms in Rwanda. Data analysis was done using a regression model. The study found that corporate diversify Growth and firm size were found to be negatively related to financial performance of manufacturing firms. The correlation results were found to be weak but moderate and financial performance of manufacturing firm. From the descriptive results, it was found that a few selected manufacturing firms had diversified their products. The mean value of the selected manufacturing firms that level of corporate

diversification is moderate. Firm size and financial performance was found to have a weak positive relationship which was represented by R =growth of the firm and financial performance of manufacturing firms. From the model of coefficients, corporate diversification was found to be statistically significant in the model. This is because its p value was lower than 5%. The research hypothesis of the study which predicts a positive relationship between corporate diversification and financial performance of the selected manufacturing firms in Rwanda. Further, it was of firm size and growth of listed manufacturing firms were statistically insignificant. The results obtained were as follows $p=0.007$ and $p=0.094$.

Murungi Deborah Justine (2016) studied cost control and profitability of manufacturing companies in Rwanda, a case study of BRALIRWA Ltd. BRALIRWA limited is a public company limited by shares since 9th June 2010 incorporated in the Republic of Rwanda under the law no7/2009 of 27th April 2009 relating to companies and registered by the Registrar General Office under no 100004348. BRALIRWA Limited is a proudly Rwandan company with roots in the country that date back over 56 years to 1959 when the Company's flagship Rwandan beer brand, Primus, was first produced. In Gisenyi. It was the first company listed on the Rwanda Stock Exchange (RSE) as from 31st January, 2011 and since then it has grown into one of the largest companies in Rwanda. The general objective of study is to investigate the contribution of cost control on the profitability of manufacturing companies in Rwanda. The specific objectives were to find out the tools used by BRALIRWA to control overall cost of their products, to identify the challenges faced by the profitability of manufacturing companies and to determine the correlation coefficient between cost control and profitability of manufacturing companies in Rwanda. The research study was of paramount to the researcher, BRALIRWA, manufacturing companies, other researchers and Mount Kenya University. The research design was descriptive and correlational design to get

the information needed to conduct the research and make a necessary conclusions. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used. Primary data and secondary data were also used. The population of this research was 1031 respondents including employees of BRALIRWA Ltd. The sample size was 91 people. In this research, to collect the information, documentary analysis questionnaire were used to do the effective research. The data were analyzed through descriptive and correlational statistics using Statistical Packaging for Social Sciences (SPSS). In relation to the challenges faced by the profitability of manufacturing companies, the study found that budget system as among of the challenges, out of 91 respondents, 42 respondents selected strongly agree while 49 respondents selected agree; logistical cost challenge; out of 91 respondents, 14 respondents selected strongly agree while 77 respondents selected agree. The study analyzed the tools used by BRALIRWA to control overall cost of their products, in relation to review of internal controls as among the tools, the out of 91 respondents, 52 respondents selected strongly agree while 37 respondents selected agree. According to the correlation coefficient between cost control and profitability of manufacturing companies in Rwanda. The study used Pearson correlation coefficient and found that the coefficient r equals to 0.943.

According to Fangtao Liu *et al.* (2017) currently, the real economy is the important basis for the development of a country, especially after the global financial crisis in 2008. Given that the manufacturing industry is the main part of the national real economy, many developed and developing countries have paid considerable attention to its significance. This study focused on cost factors given that they influence national manufacturing development. Initially, this study proposed two elements, namely, manufacturing development scale and manufacturing development level, to evaluate national manufacturing development from two aspects: quantity and quality. Subsequently, they extracted a series of cost factors on the bass of the theoretical

framework and literature, including labor costs, financing costs, tax and rental costs, energy and raw materials, foreign trade exports, and business environments. On the basis of the data of 13 main manufacturing countries around the world from 2000 to 2015, they tested the influence degree of each cost element index on the scale and level of national manufacturing industry development through a two-way fixed effects model and incorporated it with the development of China's manufacturing industry as a case study. Finally, they deduced the future development trend of the manufacturing industry by specifically analyzing the cost factors affecting the development of this industry and provided policy suggestions. The main innovation and contribution of this study including: to comprehensively evaluate the national manufacturing development from two aspects, namely, "quantity" and "quality"; to identify the impact of national cost of the six elements; to demonstrate and determine the extent of its impact on the development trend of the manufacturing sector and carry out pre-judgment through empirical research on each indicator; to provide policy recommendations targeted for each of the indicators.

Research gap; according to the studies mentioned in the review of literature has contributed so much to the current study, nonetheless ,there is no study among of them has been addressed to the area of Rwanda talking to the cost behavior an analysis and financial performance of manufacturing companies in Rwanda as existing scarcity/shortage of studies information in Rwanda. This study intended to identify the effect of cost behavior analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda, using current information collected from Bralirwa Plc.

2.3 Conceptual framework

The researcher recognized the relationship between independent variable in terms of cost behavior analysis that was represented by material cost analysis; labor cost analysis; overheads cost analysis

and the dependent variable in terms of financial performance shown by profitability, liquidity, and solvability. The conceptual framework was in figure 2.1 below:

Sources: *Researcher (2021)*

Figure 2.1: Conceptual frame work

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter dealt with the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, data collection instruments, source of data include primary data and secondary data, analysis of data methods, and ethical considerations.

3.1 Research Design

This study is non-experimental research. The study applied the cross-sectional survey design where quantitative approach was focused on this study. Quantitatively the study described the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

The correlative approach was used to show the relationship between two variables, this means the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

3.2 Population of the Study

A population is a body of people or any collection of items under consideration from which samples are taken for measurement (Jill and Roger, 2003). Bralirwa Plc was the first company listed on the Rwanda Stock Exchange (RSE) as from 31st January, 2011. It has over 500 employees (www.signalhire.com/companies/bralirwa-plc 25 Sep 2021). In respect of this study, target population is 201 employees in management team in charge of Cost Behavior Analysis and Financial Performance of Bralirwa Plc, Kigali Rwanda.

3.3 Sampling

This section illustrates the way the sampling procedure was done and exactly sample size used to collect data.

3.3.1 Sample Size

A sample is a smaller set of values selected from the population, reflecting its characteristics. While sampling refers to the number of items to be selected from the population (Grilliams, 1990). To obtain good quality of data and to ensure that there is no bias in data collection, the researcher uses 10% of margin errors, while confidential result of the research is 90% of total reality. The researcher applied the formula of Taro Yamane elaborated in 1982.

Where: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ **n** = Sample Size **N** = Study Total Population **e** = Margin of error

$$n = \frac{201}{1 + (201 * (0.1)^2)} = 66.7 \approx 67$$

3.3.2 Sampling Procedures

In respect of this study, stratified and simple random sampling technique was used to select 67 respondents from target population in Bralirwa Plc.

3.4 Data Collection Techniques and Tools

In respect of this study, data collected was into two categories include primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through using questionnaires that were addressed to the selected respondents of BRALIRWA Plc.

Secondary data was conducted through accessing the published documents including annual financial reports of BRALIRWA Plc. Various tools was used to gather information from respondents. These are questionnaires, and documentary review

3.4.1 Research Questionnaire

The questionnaire is very important in data collection, because it helps to gather the information from selected respondents. In this study, the questionnaire was prepared accordingly the research questions, objectives and the topic of the research. The information was collected from questionnaire and they were filled by respondents. They were distributed to 67 respondents of BRALIRWA Plc. The questionnaire was composed by close end questions; and expectation of 100% of participation rate for responding to the questions. To design questionnaire, a researcher was used five likert scales to assess the perceptions of respondents.

Table 3.1: Likert scales of perceptions of respondents on Questionnaire Design

Strongly Agree (SA)	Agree (A)	Neutral (N)	Disagree (D)	Strongly Disagree (SD)
5	4	3	2	1

Source: *Researcher Compilation, 2021*

3.4.2 Document Review

In respect of secondary data, documentary technique was used in this research as tool which contains the information about a phenomenon that researcher wishes to study. In this study, the target documents were available annual reports of BRALIRWA Plc.

3.5 Validity and reliability tests

According to Drost (2011), reliability refers to random error in measurement. Reliability indicates the accuracy or precision of the measuring instrument. The researcher was used the test-retest reliability technique where a pilot test of questionnaires were given to INYANGE Industries. This was enabling the researcher to address errors or irregularities that appeared during the research exercise.

The researcher performed another pre-test by asking the same question in different ways or repeating it at a later stage in the questionnaire to test for consistency in the response. In this study,

reliability of the research instrument was determined by administering questionnaires BRALIRWA Plc, and after sometime administer them again. A Cronbachs Alpha coefficient value of 0.70 was used to determine the reliability of the instrument. Value above 0.70 indicated presence of reliability (internal consistency) while value below signify lack of reliability,

While Mugenda (2009) defines validity of results as a degree to which results obtained from the analysis actually represent the variables of study. Thus, validity refers to whether the findings accurately reflect the situation and are supported by evidence. Validity was established by correlating the scores with a similar instrument.

The researcher was used pre-test technique to confirm the validity of the instrument by developing a pilot set of questions and asking them to a number of people. The results of pilot questionnaire may identify a number of deficiencies such as wording and some missing elements crucial to provide an answer to the specific aspect of the research. The questions were revised and corrected accordingly before launching the questionnaire to BRALIRWA Plc.

The validity of this research instrument was measured through the opinion of experts especially the research supervisor, who is knowledgeable in this field. It was also tested during the pilot study. Any ambiguity or non-clarity in the questionnaire items clear before the questionnaire was taken to the field for data collection. The pilot study was carried out at Inyange Industries. The validity

was tested using Content Validity Index (CVI). $CVI = \frac{\text{Total numbers of relevant items in the instrument}}{\text{Total numbers of items in the instruments}}$

Table 3.2: Legend Cronbach’s Alpha test of Reliability

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.9$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable (Surveys)
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

Source: *Pre-test of reliability from SPSS Analysis (2021)*

Table 3.2: Reliability test result statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.840	12

Source: *Pre-test of reliability from SPSS Analysis (2021)*

The pre-test result was done in Inyange Industries showed the reliability statistics of 0.840 (i.e. 84.0%) categorized as good questionnaire. This helped and allowed to continue with the study at Bralirwa Plc.

3.6 Data Processing

After data collection, data processing was concerned with putting responses into meaningful categories where it consists of editing, coding, classifying and tabulation.

Editing: this research was focusing the process of going through the questionnaire to ensure that the errors and omission are corrected. Editing involves the inspection and if necessary, connections of each questionnaire or observation form; the basic purpose of editing is to impose some minimum quality standards on the raw data.

Coding: is the code in the procedure by which data are categorized. Through coding, the raw data are transformed into symbols usually numerals that may be tabulated and counted. The transformation is not automatic; however, it involves judgment on the part of coder.

Classifying: focuses on the classifying the answers acquired, coded and tallies use to determine the frequencies of each response. Similar responses would be grouped according to their different categories.

Tabulation: refers to the part of technical process on statistical analysis of data that involves counting to determine the number cases that fall into various categories. Thus, after eliminating errors, codes are assigned to each answer.

3.7 Methods of Data Analysis

Data analysis is preceded by data cleaning. The latter was performed in SPSS IBM 22 version through the removal and harmonization of typographical errors on key variables to avoid their inconsistencies and duplication. In addition, the completeness of data was performed to see whether all information for variable have been entered correctly. After the discovery of the error the data was reviewed the responded questionnaires to fill the missing information. In case the information is found to be missing on the questionnaire, the researcher called the respondent to request the answer for the missing information. Data reliability analysis is performed in SPSS IBM 22.0 through Cronbach's Alpha reliability test to check the consistency in data that have been corrected using five Likert scales questionnaire.

Descriptive statistical methods

In data analysis, descriptive statistical methods and correlation matrix test are carried out to present the background information against the study variables and establish the strength of the relationship between variables respectively.

Linear Regression analysis

The study uses the linear regression test to analyze Cost Behavior Analysis in terms of Material Cost analysis; Labor Cost analysis; Overheads Cost analysis as independent variables, within Financial Performance of Manufacturing Industries in terms of "profitability ratios; liquidity ratios; and solvability ratios" as dependent variables. The models are as follows: X= independent variable = Cost Behavior Analysis which has three indicators: x1= Material Cost analysis; x2= Labor Cost analysis; x3= Overheads Cost analysis.

While Y= dependent variable = financial performance of Manufacturing Industries which had also indicators follows: y1= Profitability; y2= Liquidity; and y3= Solvability. Based on these variables,

the following functions have been set: $Y = f(X)$, Therefore, $y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ function. Based on these functional relationship the following econometric models has been formulated using multiple regression or polynomial models: $Y = f(X)$ therefore, $y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \varepsilon$; Where, $\beta_0 =$ Constant, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ are coefficients of determination.

3.8 Limitations of the Study

The faced different challenges in data collection. First challenge faced was a delay of the study caused by unplanned pandemic of COVID-19 that causes the closure of schools at least the worldwide, and in country, Rwanda. To obtain secondary data could be also difficult because it was required to call CEO to allow for collecting financial statements at end of year 2017-2020. Availability of respondents as expected could be also difficult because of pandemic of COVID-19 limited the movement during the period of data gatherings. The researcher, to overcome those constraints the researcher took permission to accomplish her research where she spent two weeks to collect data related research topic from BRALIRWA Plc, and researcher used different reports, for the questionnaires delay in hands of respondents, she used to call them and ask for an assistance.

3.9 Ethical Considerations

To ensuring the confidentiality of information was provided by respondents, and ascertaining the practice of ethics of this study, the following activities were implemented by the researcher: the respondents were coded instead of reflecting the names. The researcher was requested the respondents to sign in the informed consent form for those met in data collection, acknowledge the authors quoted in this study and the author of the standardized instrument through citations and referencing. The research presented the findings in a generalized manner.

CHAPTER 4

RESEARCH FINDINGS

This chapter presents the findings obtained from data collected from Respondents of Bralirwa Plc, Kigali office. Data were gathered from respondents in two weeks and half by responding to the questions from questionnaires. After data collection, the findings indicated that the participation rate was 100.0% of responding to the questions. This helped to continue with editing, coding, recording, and made statistical tables.

Data were analyzed quantitatively using computer software while the results were presented and interpreted in accordance with the research objectives. It is therefore this chapter has four sections including profile of respondents; descriptive statistics from perceptions of respondents; inferential analysis included by correlation coefficient analysis and linear regression analysis and lastly, financial analysis ratios from Bralirwa Plc reports.

4.1 Profile of Respondents

This sub-section presents social demographic characteristics of respondents of Bralirwa Plc include gender, ages, educational level, experiences of respondents and types of costs appeared mostly in Bralirwa Plc. Findings in table 4.1 presents the results from respondents' profile.

Table 4.1: Findings on Social Demographic characteristics of Respondents

	Data	Frequencies	Percentages
Gender	Male	46	68.7
	Female	21	31.3
	Total	67	100.0
Ages	21 and 30 years old	16	23.9
	31 and 40 years old	27	40.3
	41 and 50 years old	16	23.9
	51 years and above	8	11.9
	Total	67	100.0
Highest Education Level	Masters and above	8	11.9
	Bachelor's degree	55	82.1
	Secondary level	4	6.0
Experiences	Total	67	100.0
	Between 1-2years	9	13.4
	3-4years	17	25.4
	5-6 years	31	46.3
	7years and above	10	14.9
Total	67	100.0	

Source: Field Data, (2021)

Findings in table 4.1 showed the gender distribution of respondents confirmed that majority males than females among participants of this study. This justified by 68.7% respondents were males while 31.3% respondents were females among participants of this survey in Bralirwa Plc.

Concerning to ages of respondents; respondents from Bralirwa were mature enough to be able for participating in this survey and provide real information about cost behavior analysis of Bralirwa Plc where 23.9% of respondents were between 21 and 30 years old; 40.3% respondents were in range between 31 and 40 years old; 23.9% respondents were between 41 and 50 years old while 11.9% respondents were in range of 51 years and above.

Education level of participants in survey was confirmed by 82.1% of respondents have bachelor's degree; 11.9% respondents have masters and above while only 6.0% respondents have secondary school but they started to apply university for scaling education level. As for experience of

respondents, 13.4% respondents have experience between 1-2years in cost management in manufacturing company; 25.4% of respondents have 3-4years; 46.3% respondents have 5-6 years while 14.9% respondents have 7years and above. With experiences of respondents, they have enough experiences and understood Bralirwa Plc cost behavior analysis.

4.2 Descriptive Statistic Analysis

Cost, is an expenditure or outlay of cash, other property, capital stock, or services or the incurring of a liability therefor, identified with goods or services acquired or with any loss incurred and measured by the amount of cash paid or payable or the market value of other property, capital stock, or services rendered in exchange or in other situations, any commonly accepted basis of valuation. The costs are classified as follows (i) Variable costs; (ii) Fixed costs, and (iii) Mixed costs: (a) Semi-variable costs and (b) Semi-fixed costs/step-costs/step variable costs.

During this study at Bralirwa Plc, the types of cost used by Bralirwa Plc are labour costs on the rate of 37.3%; material costs has rate of 29.9% and overhead costs was 32.8% of the use in Bralirwa plc. The perception of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; and relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda were presented in this section.

4.2.1 Perception of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis

Literally, the uniqueness of material cost analysis lies in the allocation of all production costs either to the intended output (the product), or the unplanned output (all waste occurring over all the production steps). Thereby, the transparency of material flows and the associated costs increases

considerably; inefficiencies concerning material and energy consumption which are revealed, and hidden costs uncovered. Findings in table 4.2 presented the perceptions of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of Bralirwa PLC as follows.

Table 4.2: Perception of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of Bralirwa PLC

Perception of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis	SA		A		N		D		SD		Mean	Std. Dev
	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%		
Analysis of Raw materials cost help to existent profitability;	36	53.7	24	35.8	3	4.5	2	3.0	2	3.0	1.656	.9302
Material cost analysis help in decision making of manufacturing;	31	46.3	21	31.3	13	19.4	1	1.5	1	1.5	1.81	.909
Material cost analysis help to assess the operating efficiency of the firm;	43	64.2	12	17.9	6	9.0	6	9.0	0	0.0	1.63	.982
Direct Material Cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the profitable of the firm;	25	37.3	38	56.7	2	3.0	1	1.5	1	1.5	1.73	.730
Material cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the financial position of the firm;	44	65.7	14	20.9	6	9.0	2	3.0	1	1.5	1.54	.893
Material cost analysis assess the long term position of the firm;	13	19.4	45	67.2	1	1.5	6	9.0	2	3.0	2.09	.917
Material cost analysis help to measure the efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits;	6	9.0	58	86.6	2	3.0	1	1.5	0	0.0	1.970	.4253
Material cost analysis help to know how well a company at running its business is;	35	52.2	29	43.3	1	1.5	1	1.5	1	1.5	1.57	.743
Material cost analysis help to know if the company is making any money;	5	7.5	58	86.6	2	3.0	1	1.5	1	1.5	2.029	.5496
Material cost analysis help to know how profitable is the company compared with its competitors.	5	7.5	53	79.1	1	1.5	7	10.4	1	1.5	2.194	.7831
Overall Average Mean and Standard Deviation											1.822	0.786

Source: Field Data (2021)

Findings in table 4.2 stated that analysis of raw materials cost helped to existent profitability in Bralirwa Plc, stated by 89.6% of respondents. Material cost analysis helped in decision making of manufacturing, confirmed by 77.6% of respondents. Material cost analysis helped to assess the operating efficiency of the firm, stated by 82.1% of respondents; direct material cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the profitable of the firm, stated by 94.0% of respondents; material

cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the financial position of the firm, agreed and strongly agreed by 86.6% of respondents; material cost analysis assessed the long term position of the firm, confirmed by 86.6% of respondents; material cost analysis helped to measure the efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits stated by 95.5% of respondents; and material cost analysis helped to know how well a company at running its business is, argued by 95.5% of respondents in Bralirwa Plc.

According to the findings from perception of respondents on the effect of material cost analysis has presented overall average of (\bar{x} =**1.822** and **SD=0.786**) on the financial performance of Bralirwa PLC; this means there is reasonably mean and evidence of presence of the fact and heterogeneity of responses. After planning and implementing material cost analysis, the people in manufacturing company is responsible for the single production process that should start with the analysis of the data and develop the necessary actions to improve the process. Some changes in the process can be made without much coordination; here, the improvement measures are executed directly after the material cost analysis and this influenced the manufacturing performance. Most production processes are already optimized; changing a running system is complex, and plant managers are rather reluctant to make changes for what are often only minor improvements that may affect business performance.

Eduardo Hebling *et al.*, (2013) assessed the total cost of direct and indirect materials used in Class III, IV and V composite resin direct restorations. Methods, the calculation of costs was based on the method of variable costing system. A list of the materials was obtained by a panel of experts and based on the excellence standards established in the literature for dental team treatment. The cost considered for each material was obtained from an average of the costs found in the regional supplier market (US\$1.0=R\$2.12). The repetitions were obtained from Class III, IV and V cavities

in artificial pre-manufactured teeth. The cavities were classified as shallow, medium and deep. The materials were quantified for each type of preparation. Seven brands of composite resins were used and weighed on a precision scale after their insertion in each cavity. The data were analyzed by descriptive statistics and non-parametric Friedman's test ($\alpha=0.05$). Results, the mean costs were US\$7.96 (R\$16.88) for Class III restoration, US\$8.13 (R\$17.24) for Class IV, and US\$7.84 (R\$16.62) for Class V. There was statistically significant difference in cost between the types of cavities and depth classification. The small cost difference among the different resin brands resulted in no statistically significant differences in the total cost of the restorations. Conclusions: The costs obtained in this survey may be used in the calculation of the final cost of restorative procedures, helping in the management of public or private dental care services.

4.2.2 Perceptions of respondents on the effect of labor cost analysis

Findings showed that higher labor costs means higher wage rates and employee benefits made workers better off, but they can reduce companies' profits, the number of jobs, and the hours each person works. Overtime pay, hiring subsidies, the minimum wage, and payroll taxes are just a few of the policies that affect labor costs. The results in table 4.3 showed the perceptions of respondents on the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc.

Table 4.3: Perceptions of respondents on the effect of labor cost analysis on financial performance of Bralirwa Plc

Perceptions of respondents on the effect of labor cost analysis	SA		A		N		D		SD		Mean	Std. Dev
	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%		
Analysis of labor cost help Bralirwa Plc in efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits;	35	52.2	28	41.8	3	4.5	1	1.5	0	0.0	1.5672	.7224
Bralirwa Plc analyze a company's fixed labor to understand what's going on behind closed doors in terms of profitability; effectiveness and efficiency;	26	38.8	38	56.7	2	3.0	0	0.0	1	1.5	1.6716	.6127
Direct labor costs analysis used to track employment data and the way supervisors periodically evaluate subordinates' performance;	26	38.8	39	58.2	2	3.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1.64	.542
A labor-cost analysis often calls for a sharp-edged investigative ability, a devotion to accuracy, an innate sense of operational efficiency;	40	59.7	19	28.4	6	9.0	2	3.0	0	0.0	1.55	.784
Labor costs are helping an organization stay in a competitive position;	18	26.9	38	56.7	2	3.0	5	7.5	4	6.0	2.09	1.069
They're accelerating its commercial demise;	11	16.4	51	76.1	1	1.5	4	6.0	0	0.0	1.97	.651
An increase of the amount of labor is associated with an increase in service and conformance quality which, in turn, is associated with an increase in profitability;	5	7.5	50	74.6	3	4.5	6	9.0	0	0.0	2.28	.901
Low cost of labor enhance the financial performance of manufacturing companies;	35	52.2	27	40.3	3	4.5	2	3.0	0	0.0	1.58	.721
There are labour related bonuses to ensure that the company's workforce performs to its best while minimizing losses in Bralirwa Ltd;	24	35.8	39	58.2	2	3.0	0	0.0	2	3.0	1.76	.780
Bralirwa company hire experienced labour force to reduce the costs involved during trails and training.	40	59.7	18	26.9	6	9.0	3	4.5			1.58	.838
Overall Average Mean and Standard Deviation											1.7688	0.762

Source: Field Data (2021)

The above table 4.3 revealed that analysis of labor cost helps Bralirwa Plc in efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits confirmed by 94.0% respondents; Bralirwa Plc analyze a company's fixed labor to understand what's going on behind closed doors in terms of profitability; effectiveness and efficiency stated by 95.5% respondents; Direct labor costs analysis used to track employment data and the way supervisors periodically evaluate subordinates' performance agreed and strongly agreed by 97.0% respondents; a labor-cost analysis often calls

for a sharp-edged investigative ability, a devotion to accuracy, an innate sense of operational efficiency agreed and strongly agreed by 88.1% respondents; labor costs are helping an organization stay in a competitive position stated by 83.6% respondents; they're accelerating its commercial demise stated by 92.5% respondents; an increase of the amount of labor is associated with an increase in service and conformance quality which, in turn, is associated with an increase in profitability stated by 82.1% respondents; low cost of labor enhance the financial performance of manufacturing companies stated by 92.5% respondents; there are labour related bonuses to ensure that the company's workforce performs to its best while minimizing losses in Bralirwa Ltd stated by 94.0% respondents; and Bralirwa company hire experienced labour force to reduce the costs involved during trails and training agreed and strongly agreed by 86.6% respondents.

According the results in interpretation of mean and standard deviation on the perceptions of respondents about effect of labor cost analysis has presented overall average of ($\bar{x} = 1.7688$ and $SD = 0.762$) in influencing financial performance of Bralirwa Plc; this means that there is realistic mean and the evidence of existing fact and heterogeneity of responses.

According to the study Zeynep Ton (2009) determined staffing levels is an important decision in retail operations. While the costs of increasing labor are obvious and easy to measure, the benefits are often indirect and not immediately felt. One benefit of increased labor is improved quality. The objective was to examine the effect of labor on profitability through its impact on quality. Using longitudinal data from stores of a large retailer, he find that increasing the amount of labor at a store is associated with an increase in profitability through its impact on conformance quality but not its impact on service quality. While increasing labor is associated with an increase in service quality, in this setting there is no significant relationship between service quality and profitability. Findings highlight the importance of attending to process discipline in certain service settings.

4.2.3 Perceptions of respondents on the effect of overheads cost analysis

Costs are caused by resources where some resources, such as indirect skilled labor, are costly to adjust in the short term so are predisposed to generating fixed costs. Findings in table 4.4 showed the perceptions of respondents on effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

Table 4.4: Perceptions of respondents on effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda;

Perceptions of respondents on effect of overheads cost analysis	SA		A		N		D		SD		Mean	Std. Dev
	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%		
Manufacturing overheads like electricity and other utilities required to run equipment in the factory augment profitability of Bralirwa Ltd;	23	34.3	40	59.7	2	3.0	0	0.0	2	3.0	1.78	.775
Overheads cost analysis like depreciation of manufacturing equipment strengthen liquidity of manufacturing company;	37	55.2	21	31.3	6	9.0	3	4.5	0	0.0	1.63	.832
Analysis of factory supplies for manufacturing processes increases performance of company;	15	22.4	44	65.7	1	1.5	6	9.0	1	1.5	2.01	.862
administrative overheads analysis in product quality inspectors, and managers for the factory increase financial performance of company;	8	11.9	56	83.6	2	3.0	1	1.5	0	0.0	1.94	.457
Overheads cost analysis in maintenance workers and repair parts for the equipment increase performance;	27	40.3	32	47.8	3	4.5	3	4.5	2	3.0	1.82	.936
Material handlers, such as forklift operators is overheads cost analysis of Bralirwa Plc;	24	35.8	35	52.2	3	4.5	3	4.5	2	3.0	1.8657	.91941
Property taxes and insurance on the facilities and equipment are among overheads cost analysis encourage Bralirwa Plc;	31	46.3	31	46.3	2	3.0	2	3.0	1	1.5	1.6716	.80506
Overhead costs of your company consist of significant portion of your costs;	25	37.3	33	49.3	5	7.5	3	4.5	1	1.5	1.8358	.86334
Bralirwa company has an overhead costing policy that allocates all indirect costs to production;	30	44.8	20	29.9	6	9.0	6	9.0			1.8657	.75670
Bralirwa company overheads include items like depreciation, rent, factory equipment, supplies, costs, insurance licensing and other costs in that capacity.	30	44.8	20	29.9	6	9.0	6	9.0	5	7.5	2.0448	1.26051
Overall Average Mean and Standard Deviation											1.678	0.7697

Source: Field Data (2021)

Findings in table 4.4 stated that manufacturing overheads like electricity and other utilities required to run equipment in the factory augment profitability of Bralirwa Ltd, stated by 94.0% respondents; overheads cost analysis like depreciation of manufacturing equipment strengthen liquidity of manufacturing company, confirmed by 86.6% respondents; analysis of factory supplies for manufacturing processes increases performance of company, agreed and strongly agreed by 88.1% of respondents; administrative overheads analysis in product quality inspectors, and managers for the factory increase financial performance of company, argued by 95.5% respondents; overheads cost analysis in maintenance workers and repair parts for the equipment increase performance stated by 88.1% respondents. Material handlers, such as forklift operators is overheads cost analysis of Bralirwa Plc stated by 88.1% respondents; property taxes and insurance on the facilities and equipment are among overheads cost analysis encourage Bralirwa Plc agreed and strongly agreed by 92.5% respondents; overhead costs of your company consist of a significant portion of your costs stated by 86.6% respondents; Bralirwa company has an overhead costing policy that allocates all indirect costs to production; stated by 88.1% respondents; and Bralirwa company overheads include items like depreciation, rent, factory equipment, supplies, costs, insurance licensing and other costs in that capacity agreed and strongly agreed by 74.6% respondents. According to the study of Anderson *et al.*, (2003) cost management is one of the most significant issues in company performance and company financial management which any enterprise has to solve as in the periods of declines of sales revenues, as well as during their growth.

Omar Fikrat Fateh Tarzibashi (2019) investigate the impact of the magnitude of overhead costs on the results of ABC and TDABC differences. A quantitative research method was used and data were gathered through an extensive literature review. A total of 170 articles that included both ABC and TDABC were found and 37 were used because only 37 articles included both the

application of the systems and the comparison of the results of the systems. Correlation analysis and regression analysis were used to test whether there is a relationship between overhead costs and the differences in the results of ABC and TDABC systems. The results indicated that there is a statistically significant relationship between the total amount of overhead cost and the differences in the results of ABC and TDABC systems. Accordingly, when the overhead costs are increased, the TDABC system produces more different results than ABC. Based on this finding, the practical implication of this study seems to portray that companies with high overhead costs using the TDABC system rather than the ABC have the advantage of ascertaining product costing differently, which are more accurate.

4.2.4 Relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

Cost management is one of the most significant issues in company performance and company financial management which any enterprise has to solve as in the periods of declines of sales revenues, as well as during their growth. In this study was designed and tested by several regression models that could be suitable for cost behavior prediction and subsequent decision-making based on these predictions. Findings in table 4.5 present Perceptions of respondents on Relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

Table 4.5: Findings on the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

Cost behavior analysis and financial performance	SA		A		N		D		SD		Mean	Std. Dev
	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%	fi	%		
Cost behavior analysis in management help to understand how operating costs change in relation to a change in the level of activity;	10	14.9	47	70.1	3	4.5	6	9.0	1	1.5	2.119	.8261
Analysis of direct materials, direct labor, and overhead costs are incurred from developing a product to boost the financial performance of the manufacturing industry;	32	47.8	27	40.3	3	4.5	4	6.0	1	1.5	1.731	.9142
Variations in the cost driver of cost behavior analysis explain the variations in the related total costs that affect financial performance;	38	56.7	24	35.8	1	1.5	2	3.0	2	3.0	1.597	.9055
Cost behavior is summarized into a linear cost function within a relevant range facilitate the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc;	24	35.8	40	59.7	1	1.5	2	3.0	0	0.0	1.716	.6468
Material cost analysis of Bralirwa help to strengthen profitability in Rwanda;	40	59.7	19	28.4	6	9.0	0	0.0	2	3.0	1.582	.8901
Labor cost analysis enhanced the financial performance of Bralirwa Ltd;	13	19.4	46	68.7	1	1.5	6	9.0	1	1.5	2.044	.8426
Overheads Cost analysis helps to reduce useless waste and enhance the performance of Bralirwa Ltd;	23	34.3	40	59.7	1	1.5	1	1.5	2	3.0	1.791	.8078
Bralirwa company have an effective direct and indirect cost management policy that helps to reach on financial performance;	33	49.3	28	41.8	4	6.0	0	0.0	2	3.0	1.656	.8448
Bralirwa company has an integrated material management system that ensures proper purchase, delivery, and handling/storage;	27	40.3	34	50.7	2	3.0	3	4.5	1	1.5	1.761	.8364
Bralirwa company has a costing system that allocates indirect labor costs to production for easy computation of total labor costs.	21	31.3	35	52.2	5	7.5	3	4.5	3	4.5	1.985	.9922
Overall Average Mean and Standard Deviation											1.798	0.851

Source: Field Data (2021)

Findings in table 4.5 confirmed that cost behavior analysis in management help to understand how operating costs change in relation to a change in level of activity, stated by 85.1% respondents; analysis of direct materials, direct labor, and overhead costs are incurred from developing a product to boost financial performance of manufacturing industry, agreed and strongly agreed by 88.1% respondents; variations in the cost driver of cost behavior analysis explain the variations in the

related total costs that affect financial performance, strongly agreed and agreed by 92.5% respondents; cost behavior is summarized into a linear cost function within a relevant range facilitate financial performance of Bralirwa Plc, confirmed by 95.5% respondents; material cost analysis of Bralirwa helped to strengthen profitability in Rwanda, argued by 88.1% respondents; labor cost analysis enhanced financial performance of Bralirwa Ltd, stated by 88.1% respondents; overheads cost analysis help to reduce useless waste and enhance performance of Bralirwa Ltd, confirmed by 94.0% respondents; Bralirwa company have an effective direct and indirect cost management policy that help to reach on financial performance, stated by 91.0% respondents; Bralirwa company has an integrated material management system that ensures proper purchase, delivery and handling/storage, confirmed by 91.0% of respondents; and Bralirwa company has a costing system that allocates indirect labor costs to production for easy computation of total labour costs, confirmed by 83.6% of respondents.

4.2.5 Findings on the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc;

Financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. The term is also used as a general measure of a firm's overall financial health over a given period. With perceptions of respondents, table 4.6 confirming views of respondents about indicators of financial performance of Bralirwa Plc.

Table 4.6: Perceptions of respondents on financial performance of Bralirwa Plc

Perceptions of respondents on financial performance	SA		A		N		D		SD		Mean	Std. Dev
	fi	%										
There is a high client retention rate for Bralirwa Plc;	5	7.5	53	79.1	1	1.5	6	9.0	2	3.0	2.209	.8264
Gross profit margin is enough to generate net profit in profitability ratio of Bralirwa Plc after subtracting the cost of goods sold;	35	52.2	28	41.8	1	1.5	2	3.0	1	1.5	1.597	.7988
Net profit margin is sufficient in a profitability ratio comparing to all costs for the business;	43	64.2	5	7.5	6	9.0	0	0.0	13	19.4	2.029	1.585
Working capital is enough in Bralirwa as a measure of the business's available operating liquidity;	47	70.1	11	16.4	1	1.5	0	0.0	8	11.9	1.552	1.004
The business's ability of Bralirwa Plc is able to handle short-term and long term obligations;	8	11.9	27	40.3	13	19.4	11	16.4	8	11.9	2.761	1.219
Inventory turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency to measure how many times per accounting period this company sold its entire inventory;	30	44.8	21	31.3	13	19.4	3	4.5	0	0.0	1.835	.8977
Total asset turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate revenue;	5	7.5	53	79.1	1	1.5	5	7.5	3	4.5	2.223	.8672
ROE indicates effectively how well the business utilize equity investments to earn profit for investors;	36	53.7	28	41.8	2	3.0	1	1.5	0	0.0	1.522	.6362
ROA is an indicator of how well the Bralirwa is managing its available resources and assets to net higher profits;	18	26.9	46	68.7	1	1.5	1	1.5	1	1.5	1.820	.6725
Return on investment is highly demonstrated in the financial analysis of Bralirwa Plc.	58	86.6	7	10.4	1	1.5	1	1.5	0	0.0	2.179	.5201
Overall Average Mean and Standard Deviation											1.972	0.902

Source: *Field Data (2021)*

Findings in table 4.6 confirmed that there is a high client retention rate for Bralirwa Plc stated by 86.6% of respondents; the Gross profit margin is enough to generate a net profit in profitability ratio of Bralirwa Plc after subtracting the cost of goods sold confirmed by 94.0% of respondents; the Net profit margin is sufficient in a profitability ratio comparing to all costs for the business stated by 71.6% respondents; working capital is enough in Bralirwa as a measure of the business's available operating liquidity stated by 86.6% respondents; the business's ability of

Bralirwa Plc is able to handle short-term and long term obligations, agreed and strongly agreed by 52.2% respondents; inventory turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency to measure how many times per accounting period this company sold its entire inventory, stated by 76.1% respondents; total asset turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate revenue, confirmed by 86.6% respondents; ROE indicates effectively how well the business utilize equity investments to earn profit for investors, stated by 95.5% respondents; ROA is an indicator of how well the Bralirwa is managing its available resources and assets to net higher profits, stated by 95.5% respondents; and Return on investment is highly demonstrated in the financial analysis of Bralirwa Plc, confirmed by 97.0% respondents. These findings supported by secondary data, financial performance analysis situation of Bralirwa PLc.

Financial performance analysis situation of Bralirwa PLc

The overall financial performance improved compared to 2017, despite the challenging business environment. Revenue management combined with a focus on cost savings as well as operational efficiencies, positively impacted the 2017-2020. Statement of financial position and of comprehensive income as follows:

Table 4.7: Financial performance analysis situation of Bralirwa PLC from year 2017-2018

Results in Rwf millions	2018	2017	Change (%)
Revenue	98,954	86,354	14.6%
EBIT	18,441	14,706	25.4%
EBITDA	30,944	28,308	9.3%
Net Profit	7,242	5,079	42.6%
Dividend (proposed)	5,657	3,857	46.7%
Free Operating Cash flow	(7,870)	574	-1471.1%
Statement of financial position in Rwf millions			
Total Assets	134,801	127,729	5.5%
Net Working Capital	(23,129)	(17,109)	35.2%
Shareholder's equity	39,076	35,691	9.5%
Net debt	47,686	42,240	12.9%
Results and Statement of financial position per share (1 Rwf)			
Weighted Average Number of Shares	1,028,570,000	1,028,570,000	0.0%
Earnings per share 'Rwf	7.04	4.94	42.5%
Dividend Proposed 'Rwf	5.50	3.75	46.7%
Free Operating Cash (deficit) flow 'Rwf	(7.65)	0.56	-1466.1%
Employees in Numbers			
Average Number of Employees	538	546	-1.5%
Key Ratios (in %)			
EBIT as % of Revenue	18.6%	17.0%	9.4%
Net Profit as % of Average Shareholder's Equity	18.5%	14.2%	30.3%
Net Debt/EBITDA	154.1%	149.2%	3.3%
EBITDA/Interest expenses (times covered)	382.3%	331.0%	15.5%
RONA	10.4%	7.2%	44.4%
Cash Conversion Rate	-108.7%	11.3%	-1061.9%
Dividend % Payout (% of Net Profit)	78.1%	75.9%	2.9%

Source: Secondary data, annual reports and accounts of Bralirwa PLC 2017-2018

Statement of financial position and of comprehensive income in 2017 as follows: Net debt improved by 3.1% to Rwf 42.2 billion (2016: Rwf 43.6 billion). Total payables reduced by 24.0% to Rwf 34.8 billion (2016: Rwf 45.8 billion). This was due to final payments made related to the five year investment program we concluded in 2016.

Revenue declined by 2.8% to Rwf 86.4 billion (2016: Rwf 88.8 billion), driven by a reduction in total sales volume of 12.4% following the price increases in soft drinks and mainstream beer. Decreased cost of sales by 4.8% to Rwf 60.1 billion (2016: Rwf 63.1 billion), driven by lower volume, cost savings, efficiencies and mix effects and despite higher depreciation and raw material costs. Total depreciation was up 19.2% to Rwf 13.5 billion (2016: Rwf 11.3 billion). This was due to the adjustment in the useful life of the returnable bottles from 7 to 6 years (Rwf 1.7 billion).

Increased other income by 244.7% to Rwf 5.3 billion (2016: Rwf 1.5 billion) mainly driven by the release of the deposit liability (Rwf 3.6 billion).

The other operating expenses reflect the impairment of the Bramin long term loan of Rwf 2.4 billion. Net finance cost decreased by 26.1% to Rwf 7.0 billion (2016: Rwf 9.5 billion).

Results from operating activities increased by 21.3% to Rwf 14.7 billion (2016: Rwf 12.1 billion) and profit and total comprehensive income for the year 2017 increased by 263.3% to Rwf 5.1 billion (2016: Rwf 1.4 billion). This improved earnings per share to Rwf 4.94 (2016: Rwf 1.36).

The overall financial performance improved in 2018, despite the challenging business environment.

Revenue management combined with a focus on cost savings as well as operational efficiencies, positively impacted the 2018 statement of financial position and of comprehensive income as follows:

1. Net debt increased by 12.9% to Rwf 47.7 billion in 2018 (2017: Rwf 42.2 billion).
2. Total payables reduced by 11.8% to Rwf 30.7 billion in 2018 (2017: Rwf 34.7 billion).
3. Revenue improved by 14.6% to Rwf 99.0 billion in 2018 (2018: Rwf 86.4 billion), driven by a favourable mix and strong volume growth which increased by 14.6%.

4. Increased cost of sales by 10.1% to Rwf 66.2 billion in 2018 (2017: Rwf 60.1 billion), driven by higher volume, cost savings, efficiencies and mixed effects and despite higher raw material costs.

5. The other operating expenses reflect the impairment of the Bramin long term loan of Rwf 0.3 billion (2017: Rwf 2.4 billion).

6. Net finance cost increased by 15.7% to Rwf 8.1 billion in 2018 (2017: Rwf 7.0 billion).

Consequently, our results from operating activities increased by 25.4% to Rwf 18.4 billion (2017: Rwf 14.7 billion), and profit and total comprehensive income for the year 2018 increased by 42.6% to Rwf 7.2 billion (2017: Rwf 5.1 billion). This resulted in an improved earnings per share of Rwf 7.04 in 2018 (2017: Rwf 4.94).

Table 4.8: Operational review and summary results for the year ended 31st December 2017-2018

Rwf millions	2018	2017	Change (%)
Revenue	98,954	86,354	14.6%
Results from operating activities	18,441	14,706	25.4%
Net finance cost	(8,095)	(6,997)	15.7%
Profit before income tax	10,346	7,709	34.2%
Income tax expense	(3,104)	(2,631)	18.0%
Profit and total comprehensive income for the year	7,242	5,078	42.6%

Source: Secondary data, annual reports and accounts of Bralirwa PLC 2017-2018

Top line, volume and revenue, improved substantially driven by Bralirwa's brand investments and new products introduction. Revenue was 14.6% higher than last year at Rwf 99.0 billion (2017: Rwf 86.4 billion), due to a favorable mix and strong volume growth. The market recovered from the prior years' price increases, but remained very competitive with still constrained consumer spending. In 2018, pricing was taken on soft drinks for the first time in two years to compensate for increased fixed costs from operations, and currency depreciation resulted in higher raw material

and other costs. The adverse impact on volume was in line with expectations. A continued focus on cost savings combined with operational efficiencies resulted in improved performance at the bottom line. Bralirwa's results from operating activities increased by 25.4% to Rwf 18.4 billion (2017: Rwf 14.7 billion), and profit and total comprehensive income for the year 2018 increased by 42.6% to Rwf 7.2 billion (2017: Rwf 5.1 billion). This resulted in an improved earnings per share of Rwf 7.04 (2017: Rwf 4.94).

Table 4.9: Financial performance analysis situation of Bralirwa PLC in the year 2019-2020

Results in Rwf millions	2020	2019	Change (%)
Revenue	100,521	100,691	(0.2%)
EBIT	19,826	10,667	85.9%
EBITDA	32,882	24,476	34.3%
Net Profit	9,005	1,192	655.5%
Dividend (proposed)	9,000	1,029	774.6%
Free Operating Cash flow	(6,818)	1,929	(453.4%)
Statement of financial position in Rwf millions			
Total Assets	127,271	121,741	4.5%
Net Working Capital	(30,866)	(30,923)	(0.2%)
Shareholder's equity	42,588	34,611	23.0%
Net debt	42,630	41,298	3.2%
Results and Statement of financial position per share			
Weighted Average Number of Shares	1,028,570,000	1,028,570,000	0.0%
Earnings per share 'Rwf	8.75	1.16	654.3%
Dividend Proposed 'Rwf	8.75	1.00	775.0%
Free Operating Cash (deficit) flow 'Rwf	(6.63)	1.88	(452.7%)
Employees in Numbers			
Average Number of Employees	483	509	(5.2%)
Key Ratios (in %)			
EBIT as % of Revenue	19.7%	10.6%	85.8%
Net Profit as % of Average Shareholder's Equity	21.1%	3.4%	520.6%
Net Debt/EBITDA	129.6%	168.7%	(23.2%)
EBITDA/Interest expenses (times covered)	481.3%	314.3%	53.1%
RONA	15.4%	2.1%	633.3%
Cash Conversion Rate	-75.7%	161.8%	(146.8%)
Dividend % Payout (% of Net Profit)	99.9%	86.3%	15.8%

Source: Secondary data, annual reports and accounts of Bralirwa PLC 2019-2020

Top line, the volume decreased versus last year due to Soft Drink brands decline offset by Beer brands increase. Revenue is almost flat versus last year at Rwf 101 billion (2019: Rwf 101 billion), mainly driven by favorable price effect and mix. Despite COVID-19 governmental restrictions impact, the market share slightly increased compared to last year from our brands innovation and sales operations' digitalization.

However, it remains very competitive. A continued focus on cost savings combined with operational efficiencies resulted in improved performance at the bottom line. Bralirwa Plc's results from operating activities increased by 85.9% to Rwf 19.8 billion (2019: Rwf 10.7 billion), and profit and total comprehensive income for the year 2020 increased by 665.5% to Rwf 9.0 billion (2019: Rwf 1.2 billion). This increased earnings per share of Rwf 8.75 (2019: Rwf 1.16).

Table 4.10: Operational Review and summary results for the year ended 31 December 2019-2020

Rwf millions	2020	2019	Change (%)
Revenue	100,521	100,691	(0.2%)
Results from operating activities	19,826	10,667	85.9%
Net finance cost	(6,832)	(7,788)	(12.3%)
Profit before income tax	12,994	2,879	351.3%
Income tax expense	(3,989)	(1,687)	136.5%
Profit and total comprehensive income for the year	9,005	1,192	655.5%

Source: Secondary data, annual reports and accounts of Bralirwa PLC 2019-2020

4.3 Inferential analysis

4.3.1 Correlation coefficient matrix

The measure is best used in variables that demonstrate a linear relationship between each other. A correlation matrix consists of rows and columns that show the variables. Each cell in a table contains the correlation coefficient. Table 4.11 illustrate findings on correlation matrix as follows.

Table 4.11: Correlation coefficient matrix between Variables

		Material Cost analysis	Labor Cost analysis	Overheads Cost analysis	Financial performance of manufacturing industries
Material Cost analysis	Pearson Correlation		1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1557.075			
	Covariance	23.592			
Labor Cost analysis	N	67			
	Pearson Correlation	.871**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000			
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1493.179	1888.030		
Overheads Cost analysis	Covariance	22.624	28.607		
	N	67	67		
	Pearson Correlation	.596**	.571**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
Financial performance of manufacturing industries	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	628.522	663.254	714.657	
	Covariance	9.523	10.049	10.828	
	N	67	67	67	
	Pearson Correlation	.895**	.885**	.556**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	1729.761	1882.627	728.328	2397.164
	Covariance	26.209	28.525	11.035	36.321
	N	67	67	67	67

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Findings in Table 4.11 present results from correlations coefficient matrix analysis, where results confirmed that there is a positive and very strong correlation between material cost analysis in cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries as Pearson correlation is **.895**** with the p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. This indicates that, out of the considered other factors affecting financial performance, only material Cost analysis in cost behavior analysis has significant effect of **89.5%** of all financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC, Rwanda.

The results also stated that there is positive and very strong correlation between Labor Cost analysis and the financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC as Pearson correlation is **.885**** with p-value of 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01, and this indicates that, out of the considered other factors of cost behavior analysis, Labor Cost analysis has significant relationship of **88.5%** on the financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC, Rwanda.

Lastly, findings show that there is positive and strong correlation between overheads cost analysis and financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC, Rwanda as Pearson correlation is **.556**** with p-value is 0.000, which is less than standard significance level of 0.01. This indicates that, out of the considered other factors affect financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC, Rwanda, only Overheads Cost analysis in cost behavior analysis has significant relationship of **55.6%** on the financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC, Rwanda.

4.3.2 Linear Regression Analysis Results

Linear regression analysis test is a form of inferential statistics; and the p-values that help to determine whether the relationships have observed in the sample existed in the larger population. This section helped to verify and test whether the research hypotheses are retained or rejected in the model of the study.

Table 4.12: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.921 ^a	.847	.840	2.40934

a. Predictors: (Constant), Overheads Cost analysis, Labor Cost analysis, Material Cost analysis

Findings in Table 4.12 present value of **R**, equals **.921^a** which very high and significant correlation between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; with R-square (r^2) **.847**; that means the percentage of effect on the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc (as dependent variable) are explained by independent variable indicated by cost behavior analysis represented by overheads cost analysis, labor cost analysis, material cost analysis on the rate of **84.7%**. This indicates that the model is positive and very strong, as the independent variable very highly explained the dependent variable (financial performance of Bralirwa Plc). The adjusted R-square is used to compensate for additional variable in the model. In this case, the adjusted R-square is also **84.0%**.

Table 4.13: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2031.455	3	677.152	116.652	.000^b
	Residual	365.709	63	5.805		
	Total	2397.164	66			
a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance of manufacturing industries						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Overheads Cost analysis, Labor Cost analysis, Material Cost analysis						

Findings in the ANOVA Table 4.13 present level fit mode of 116.652 with p-value of 0.000^b which is less than 0.01, set as standard significance level. This means that null hypotheses included by Ho1 stated that There are no significant effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; Ho2 said that There are no significant effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; Ho3 stated that There are no significant effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; and Ho4 said that There is no significant relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda” were all rejected; and the study retained alternative hypotheses confirmed that independent variable indicated by cost behavior analysis represented by overheads cost analysis, labor cost analysis, material cost analysis have affected positively and significantly the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc.

Table 4.14: Regression Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.624	1.702		.167	.005
	Material Cost analysis	.640	.128	.516	4.996	.000
	Labor Cost analysis	.491	.114	.435	4.311	.000
	Overheads Cost analysis	.001	.113	.000	.068	.004
a. Dependent Variable: Financial performance of manufacturing industries						

The models were **X** which is independent variable indicated by cost behavior analysis had four indicators including x1= material cost analysis; x2= labor cost analysis; x3= overheads cost

analysis; with y which is dependent variable indicated by financial performance. Based on these variables, the functions have been set as $Y = f(X)$, $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \epsilon$.

$$Y = 0.624 + 0.640x_1 + 0.491x_2 + 0.001x_3 + 1.702$$

Findings in the linear regression equation showed that financial performance of Bralirwa Plc will always depend on a constant factor of **0.624** regardless of the presence of other factors. The other variables explain that; every unit change in x_1 = Material Cost analysis; x_2 = Labor Cost analysis; x_3 = Overheads Cost analysis in cost behavior analysis will significantly change or affect financial performance of Bralirwa Plc by **0.640; 0.491; 0.001** with standard error of **1.702** in the model.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings on cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda. The conclusion and recommendations were made based on the results of this study.

5.1 Summary of Major Findings

The study was about cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda: case study of Bralirwa Plc in the period of 2017-2020. The specific objectives of this study were the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; to analyze the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; and the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda.

This study applied the cross-sectional survey design where quantitative approach. Target population is 201 employees in management team in charge of cost behavior analysis and financial performance of Bralirwa Plc, Kigali Rwanda. Stratified and simple random sampling technique was used to select 67 respondents from target population in Bralirwa Plc. Data collected was into two categories include primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected through using questionnaires that were addressed to the selected respondents of BRALIRWA Plc. Secondary data was conducted through accessing the published documents including annual financial reports of BRALIRWA Plc.

Descriptive statistics method consisted of tabulation of frequencies and percentage distribution, tendency and standard deviations, and mean. And also inferential statistical was used in this study.

Findings showed gender distribution of respondents was 68.7% of respondent's males and 31.3% respondents were females among participants of this survey in Bralirwa Plc.

5.1.1 Findings on 1st objective: the effect of material cost analysis on the financial performance of Bralirwa PLC

Findings in table 4.2 stated that analysis of raw materials cost help to existent profitability in Bralirwa Plc, Material cost analysis help in decision making of manufacturing; Material cost analysis help to assess the operating efficiency of the firm; direct material cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the profitable of the firm; material cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the financial position of the firm; material cost analysis assess the long term position of the firm; material cost analysis helped to measure the efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits; and material cost analysis help to know how well a company at running its business in Bralirwa Plc.

5.1.2 Findings on 2nd objective: the effect of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc

Findings in table 4.3 confirmed that analysis of labor cost helps Bralirwa Plc in efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits; Bralirwa Plc analyze a company's fixed labor to understand what's going on behind closed doors in terms of profitability; effectiveness and efficiency; Direct labor costs analysis used to track employment data and the way supervisors periodically evaluate subordinates' performance; a labor-cost analysis often calls for a sharp-edged investigative ability, a devotion to accuracy, an innate sense of operational efficiency; labor costs are helping an organization stay in a competitive position; they're accelerating its commercial demise; an increase of the amount of labor is associated with an increase in service and conformance quality which, in turn, is associated with an increase in profitability; low cost of labor

enhance the financial performance of manufacturing companies; there are labour related bonuses to ensure that the company's workforce performs to its best while minimizing losses in Bralirwa Ltd; and Bralirwa company hire experienced labour force to reduce the costs involved during trails and training. According the results in interpretation of mean and standard deviation on the perceptions of respondents about effect of labor cost analysis has presented overall average of (\bar{x} =1.7688 and SD=0.762) in influencing financial performance of Bralirwa Plc; this means that there is realistic mean and the evidence of existing fact and heterogeneity of responses.

5.1.3 Findings on 3rd objective: the effect of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda;

Findings in table 4.4 stated that manufacturing overheads like electricity and other utilities required to run equipment in the factory augment profitability of Bralirwa Ltd; Overheads cost analysis like depreciation of manufacturing equipment strengthen liquidity of manufacturing company; analysis of factory supplies for manufacturing processes increases performance of company; administrative overheads analysis in product quality inspectors, and managers for the factory increase financial performance of company; Overheads cost analysis in maintenance workers and repair parts for the equipment increase performance. Material handlers, such as forklift operators is overheads cost analysis of Bralirwa Plc; property taxes and insurance on the facilities and equipment are among overheads cost analysis encourage Bralirwa Plc; Overhead costs of your company consist of a significant portion of your costs; Bralirwa company has an overhead costing policy that allocates all indirect costs to production;; and Bralirwa company overheads include items like depreciation, rent, factory equipment, supplies, costs, insurance licensing and other costs in that capacity.

5.1.4 Findings on 4th objective: relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

Findings in table 4.5 confirmed that cost behavior analysis in management help to understand how operating costs change in relation to a change in level of activity; Analysis of direct materials, direct labor, and overhead costs are incurred from developing a product to boost financial performance of manufacturing industry; variations in the cost driver of cost behavior analysis explain the variations in the related total costs that affect financial performance; cost behavior is summarized into a linear cost function within a relevant range facilitate financial performance of Bralirwa Plc; material cost analysis of Bralirwa helped to strengthen profitability in Rwanda; labor cost analysis enhanced financial performance of Bralirwa Plc; overheads cost analysis help to reduce useless waste and enhance performance of Bralirwa Ltd; Bralirwa company have an effective direct and indirect cost management policy that help to reach on financial performance; Bralirwa company has an integrated material management system that ensures proper purchase, delivery and handling/storage; and Bralirwa company has a costing system that allocates indirect labor costs to production for easy computation of total labour costs.

5.2 Conclusions

According to the findings, the study findings on 1st objective confirmed that there is a positive and very strong correlation between Material Cost analysis in cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries as a Pearson correlation is 0.895** categorized as very high relationship between material cost analysis in cost behavior analysis and financial performance of Bralirwa Plc.

Findings on 2nd objective stated that there is positive and very strong correlation between labor cost analysis and the financial performance of BRALIRWA PLC as a Pearson correlation is

0.885** categorized as very high relationship between labor cost analysis and the financial performance of Bralirwa PLC of Bralirwa Plc.

The findings on 3rd objective argued that there is positive and strong correlation between overheads cost analysis and financial performance as Pearson correlation is 0.556** categorized as strong correlation overheads cost analysis and financial performance of Bralirwa Plc, Rwanda.

As conclusion, findings helped us to confirm that the problem of the study was solved, the research objectives were achieved, and research hypotheses were verified where all null hypotheses were rejected, and alternative hypothesis were retained by saying that there is significance and very high relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained in ANOVA presents level mode fit of 116.652 with p-value of 0.000^b which is less than 0.01, set as standard significance level. This means that null hypotheses included by Ho1 stated that there is no significant effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; Ho2 said that There is no significant effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; Ho3 stated that there are no significant effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda; and Ho4 said that There is no significant relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda” were all rejected; and the study retained alternative hypotheses confirmed that independent variable indicated by cost behavior analysis represented by overheads cost analysis, labor cost analysis, material cost analysis have affected positively and significantly the financial performance of Bralirwa Plc.

Even if this study found that BRALIRWA used different tools in terms of cost control, it focused only on the comparison of its performance in consecutive period rather than performance with other companies in the same industry.

Hence, BRALIRWA should use comparative analysis using comparison with other companies in the industry.

Basing on the findings related to the challenges as well as the theoretical aspects presented in the literature review this research recommends manufacturing companies of Rwanda to speed up the sensitization campaign to focus on financial report and ratio analysis as among the best tool to the profitability of manufacturing companies.

The employees are considered as a very important requirement to the operation and the procedures in every report, BRALIRWA Plc have to improve the skills of the employees working in the cost analysis.

According to the research findings related to the tools used by BRALIRWA, the researcher recommended manufacturing companies that, cost behavior analysis must have interdependent relationships that management needs to perform its activities. Since manufacturing companies contribute the highest cost among the related elements in cost of raw material, the improvement of profitability efficiency could change the overall profitability.

5.4 Areas to Further Researches

Further study should be conducted to determine other factors influencing the financial performance of manufacturing companies in Rwanda.

Future researchers should also focus on the analysis of cost in a broad sense that might help to integrate the advantages from different application cases to overcome their current disadvantage.

They should also verify if the review of financial performance systems provides a clearer notion

on profitability applications in cost behavior activities. The development of manufacturing companies is still vigorous in the following decades and the cost behavior concepts might be applied in more fields.

The other researchers should also analyze the different factors concerning the policies that should affect the financial performance of manufacturing companies.

The given study topics are follows: assessment of tools used by manufacturing companies to control overall cost of their products; assessment of challenges faced by the profitability of manufacturing companies in Rwanda.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Research Project Questionnaire

Ref: Introductory Letter to Respondent

Dear respondent,

The researcher is a student at the Kigali Independent University (ULK) pursuing Masters of Business Administration currently undertaking a research on the *“Cost Behavior Analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda: a case study of BRALIRWA PLC”* was chosen as a case study, and you have been considered to be one of the respondents. The researcher therefore requests you that you spend a few minutes of your time to answer the questions in the questionnaires by either writing in the space provided or by putting a tick in the box of your appropriate choice. All the data provided will only be used for academic purposes and will be treated with confidentiality. Your cooperation is highly appreciated.

Thank you.

MUKABATSINDA M. CLAIRE

Instructions to follow: Please tick (√) in the appropriate response according to your anticipation.

There is no right or wrong answer, only what we need from you it is your options.

SECTION A: Profile of Respondents

1. Gender

Male [] Female []

2. Age

Less than 20years

Between 21 and 30 years old []

Between 31 and 40 years old []

Between 41 and 50 years old []

51 years and above []

3. Education level

Masters and above []

Bachelor's degree []

Secondary level []

Primary level []

Other education level, specify them

4. Working Experience in BRALIRWA PLC

Less than 1year []

Between 1-2years []

Between 3-4years []

Between 5-6 years []

7years and above []

5. What are types of cost behavior analysis involved in manufacturing production of BRALIRWA,

Please, tick (v) one or more alternative for the best one in BRALIRWA LTD

a) Labour Costs []

b) Material Costs []

c) Overhead Costs []

d) Nonmanufacturing Costs []

e) Optimal cost of raw material []

f) Cost per unit []

SECTION B: Cost Behavior Analysis of BRALIRWA PLC

Please, circle only the number which corresponds to your most appropriate answer in front of every statement accordingly.

5.Strongly Agree	4. Agree	3. Neutral	2. Disagree	1. Strongly Disagree
SA	A	N	D	SD

6. What are the effects of material cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries in Rwanda?

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD
1 Analysis of Raw materials cost help to existent profitability					
2 Material cost analysis help in decision making of manufacturing					
3 Material cost analysis help to assess the operating efficiency of the firm					
4 Direct Material Cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the profitable of the firm					
5 Material cost analysis identify the reasons of change in the financial position of the firm					
6 Material cost analysis assess the long term position of the firm					
7 Material cost analysis help to measure the efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits					
8 Material cost analysis help to know how well a company at running its business is.					
9 Material cost analysis help to know if the company is making any money.					
10 Material cost analysis help to know how profitable is the company compared with its competitors					

7. What are the effects of labor cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries?

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1 Analysis of labor cost help Bralirwa Plc in efficiency with which a company turns business activity into profits					
2 Bralirwa Plc analyze a company's fixed labor to understand what's going on behind closed doors in terms of profitability; effectiveness and efficiency					
3 Direct labor costs analysis used to track employment data and the way supervisors periodically evaluate subordinates' performance					
4 A labor-cost analysis often calls for a sharp-edged investigative ability, a devotion to accuracy, an innate sense of operational efficiency					
5 Labor costs are helping an organization stay in a competitive position					
6 They're accelerating its commercial demise.					
7 An increase of the amount of labor is associated with an increase in service and conformance quality which, in turn, is associated with an increase in profitability.					
8 Low cost of labor enhance the financial performance of manufacturing companies					

9	There are labour related bonuses to ensure that the company's workforce performs to its best while minimizing losses in Bralirwa Ltd					
10	Bralirwa company hire experienced labour force to reduce the costs involved during trails and training					

8. What are the effects of overheads cost analysis on the financial performance of manufacturing industries?

		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	Manufacturing overheads like electricity and other utilities required to run equipment in the factory augment profitability of Bralirwa Ltd					
2	Overheads cost analysis like depreciation of manufacturing equipment strengthen liquidity of manufacturing company					
3	Analysis of factory supplies for manufacturing processes increases performance of company					
4	administrative overheads analysis in product quality inspectors, and managers for the factory increase financial performance of company					
5	Overheads cost analysis in maintenance workers and repair parts for the equipment increase performance					
6	Material handlers, such as forklift operators is overheads cost analysis of Bralirwa Plc					
7	Property taxes and insurance on the facilities and equipment are among overheads cost analysis encourage Bralirwa Plc					
8	Overhead costs of your company consist of significant portion of your costs					
9	Bralirwa company has an overhead costing policy that allocates all indirect costs to production					
10	Bralirwa company overheads include items like depreciation, rent, factory equipment, supplies, costs, insurance licensing and other costs in that capacity					

9. What is the relationship between cost behavior analysis and financial performance of manufacturing industries?

		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	Cost behavior analysis in management help to understand how operating costs change in relation to a change in level of activity					
2	Analysis of direct materials, direct labor, and overhead costs are incurred from developing a product to boost financial performance of manufacturing industry					
3	Variations in the cost driver of cost behavior analysis explain the variations in the related total costs that affect financial performance					
4	Cost behavior is summarized into a linear cost function within a relevant range facilitate financial performance of Bralirwa Plc					
5	Material cost analysis of Bralirwa help to strengthen profitability in Rwanda					
6	Labor cost analysis enhanced financial performance of Bralirwa Ltd					
7	Overheads Cost analysis help to reduce useless waste and enhance performance of Bralirwa Ltd					

8	Bralirwa company have an effective direct and indirect cost management policy that help to reach on financial performance					
9	Bralirwa company has an integrated material management system that ensures proper purchase, delivery and handling/storage					
10	Bralirwa company has a costing system that allocates indirect labour costs to production for easy computation of total labour costs					

SECTION C: Financial performance of Bralirwa Plc

		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	There is a high client retention rate for Bralirwa Plc					
2	Gross profit margin is enough to generate net profit in profitability ratio of Bralirwa Plc after subtracting the cost of goods sold					
3	Net profit margin is sufficient in a profitability ratio comparing to all costs for the business					
4	Working capital is enough in Bralirwa as a measure of the business's available operating liquidity					
5	Business's ability of Bralirwa Plc is able to handle short-term and long term obligations					
6	Inventory turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency to measure how many times per accounting period this company sold its entire inventory.					
7	Total asset turnover of Bralirwa is an efficiency that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate revenue					
8	ROE indicates effectively how well the business utilize equity investments to earn profit for investors.					
9	ROA is an indicator of how well the Bralirwa is managing its available resources and assets to net higher profits.					
10	Return on investment is highly demonstrated in the financial analysis of Bralirwa					

THANK YOU

APPENDIX 2: FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF BRALIRWA PLC AT THE END OF PERIOD 2017-2020

**BRASSERIES ET LIMONADERIES DU RWANDA (BRALIRWA) PLC
STATEMENT OF PROFIT OR LOSS AND OTHER COMPREHENSIVE INCOME FOR THE YEAR
ENDED 31 DECEMBER 2018**

	Notes	2018 Rwf '000	2017 Rwf '000
Revenue	8	98,953,763	86,353,934
Cost of sales		(66,160,847)	(60,078,805)
Gross profit		32,792,916	26,275,129
Other income	9	315,112	5,288,415
Selling and distribution costs		(4,502,950)	(4,089,548)
Administrative expenses		(9,863,026)	(10,404,637)
Other operating expenses		(301,000)	(2,362,921)
Total expenses		(14,666,976)	(16,857,106)
Results from operating activities	10	18,441,052	14,706,438
Finance costs		(8,094,886)	(6,997,065)
Net finance cost	12	(8,094,886)	(6,997,065)
Profit before income tax		10,346,166	7,709,373
Income tax expense	13	(3,103,735)	(2,630,632)
Profit after tax		7,242,431	5,078,741
Other Comprehensive Income		-	-
Total comprehensive income for the year		7,242,431	5,078,741
Basic earnings per share – Rwf	22	7.04	4.94

BRASSERIES ET LIMONADERIES DU RWANDA (BRALIRWA) Plc
STATEMENT OF PROFIT OR LOSS AND OTHER COMPREHENSIVE INCOME FOR THE YEAR
ENDED 31 DECEMBER 2020

Year ended 31 December	Notes	2020 Rwf '000	2019 Rwf '000
Revenue	6.1	100,520,707	100,691,220
Cost of sales		(64,323,916)	(65,814,158)
Gross profit		36,196,791	34,877,062
Other income	6.2	461,284	468,926
Selling and distribution costs		(3,178,720)	(7,856,330)
Administrative expenses		(10,083,768)	(12,428,145)
Other operating expenses		(3,569,606)	(4,394,763)
Total expenses		(16,832,094)	(24,679,238)
Results from operating activities	6.1.2	19,825,981	10,666,750
Finance costs		(6,832,002)	(7,787,763)
Net finance cost	11.1	(6,832,002)	(7,787,763)
Profit before income tax		12,993,979	2,878,987
Income tax expense	12.1	(3,988,775)	(1,687,166)
Profit after tax		9,005,204	1,191,821
Other Comprehensive Income		-	-
Total comprehensive income for the year		9,005,204	1,191,821
Basic earnings per share – Rwf	6.7	8.75	1.16

The notes on pages 55 to 110 are an integral part of these financial statements

BRASSERIES ET LIMONADERIES DU RWANDA (BRALIRWA) PLC
STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION AS AT 31 DECEMBER 2018

Assets	Notes	2018 Rwf '000	2017 Rwf '000
Assets			
Non-current assets			
Property, plant and equipment	14	87,894,633	85,764,589
Intangible assets	15	933,388	131,113
Equity Investments	16	9,224	9,224
Receivable from related parties - principal	30 (d)	4,341,181	3,997,543
Total non-current assets		92,948,426	89,902,469
Current assets			
Inventories	18	19,956,523	20,444,898
Receivable from related parties	30 (d)	381,222	814,929
Trade and other receivables	19	9,488,725	8,587,684
Tax recoverable	13 (b)	2,841,088	1,269,926
Bank and cash balances	20	8,785,307	7,308,626
Total current assets		41,852,865	38,426,063
Total assets		134,801,291	127,728,532
Equity & Liabilities			
Equity			
Share capital	21	5,142,850	5,142,850
Share premium	21	84,857	84,857
Other reserves	21	2,071,990	2,071,990
Retained earnings		31,776,519	28,381,236
Total equity		39,876,216	35,680,933
Liabilities			
Non-current liabilities			
Loans and borrowings LT	23	22,145,879	26,997,065
Deferred tax liability	25	8,597,266	7,745,331
Total non-current liabilities		30,743,145	34,742,396
Current liabilities			
Loans and borrowings ST	23	34,325,729	22,551,101
Payable to related parties	30 (d)	1,892,070	7,025,177
Trade and other payables	26	28,764,131	27,718,935
Total current liabilities		64,981,930	57,295,213
Total liabilities		95,725,075	92,037,609
Total equity and liabilities		134,801,291	127,728,532

The Board of Directors approved the financial statements set out on pages 55 to 94 on 29th March 2019 and were signed on its behalf by:

Chairman of the Board
Steven van der Borcht

Vice-Chairman of the Board
Merid Demissie

The notes set out on pages 59 to 94 are an integral part of these financial statements.

BRASSERIES ET LIMONADERIES DU RWANDA (BRALIRWA) Plc
STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION AS AT 31 DECEMBER 2020

Year ended 31 December	Notes	2020 Rwf '000	2019 Rwf '000
Assets			
Non-current assets			
Property, plant and equipment	6.6	87,554,336	85,913,732
Intangible assets	8.2	1,696,529	1,672,476
Investments	8.4	9,224	1,165,720
Receivable from related parties - principal	13.2	-	-
Total non-current assets		89,260,089	88,751,928
Current assets			
Inventories	7.1	19,962,794	18,476,947
Receivable from related parties	13.2	1,934,132	3,266,241
Trade and other receivables	7.2	10,261,117	6,530,138
Tax recoverable	12.1	895,783	451,909
Bank and cash balances	11.2	4,956,841	4,264,032
Total current assets		38,010,667	32,989,267
Total assets		127,270,756	121,741,195
Equity & Liabilities			
Equity			
Share capital	11.4	5,142,850	5,142,850
Share premium	11.4	84,857	84,857
Other reserves	11.4	2,071,990	2,071,990
Retained earnings	11.4	35,287,839	27,311,205
Total equity		42,587,536	34,610,902
Liabilities			
Non-current liabilities			
Loans and borrowings LT	11.3	11,611,544	17,412,763
Deferred tax liability	12.2	4,194,803	5,804,878
Total non-current liabilities		15,806,347	23,217,641
Current liabilities			
Loans and borrowings ST	11.3	35,975,155	28,148,479
Payable to related parties	13.2	3,880,965	6,429,647
Trade and other payables	7.3	29,020,753	29,333,526
Total current liabilities		68,876,873	63,912,652
Total liabilities		84,683,220	87,130,293
Total equity and liabilities		127,270,756	121,741,195

The Board of Directors approved the financial statements set out on pages 55 to 170 on 20 May 2021 and were signed on its behalf by:

 Chairman of the Board
 Pascal Sabrié

 Vice Chairman of the Board
 Merid Demissie